

MDMC
Master in Data Management
and Curation

MASTER IN DATA MANAGEMENT AND
CURATION

**FAIR data management for
fabrication processes.**
**A NOMAD plugin as
implemented at CNR-IFN@TN.**

Supervisor(s):
Andrea CHIAPPINI,
Mariarita DE LUCA

Candidate:
Matteo Francesco BONTORNO

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I, Matteo Francesco Bontorno, declare that this thesis entitled, ' FAIR data management for fabrication processes.' and the work presented therein are my own.

I certify that:

- This work was performed wholly or principally during MDMC internship at CNR-IFN@TN.
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- Where I have relied on the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
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- I have acknowledged all major sources of help.

Signed:

Date:

“A Ruga, capace di amore abnegante, ho imparato il valore celato nel silenzio e il fragore dei piccoli gesti”

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Abstract

This thesis presents the development of a FAIR-by-design data environment for fabrication processes at the Trento facilities of the CNR-IFN (Consiglio nazionale delle ricerche-Istituto di Fotonica e Nanotecnologie), within the framework of the NFFA-DI project. The work is structured into three main parts. First, an overview of the fabrication techniques listed in the NFFA-DI catalog and available at the Trento laboratories is provided, with a focus on deposition, etching, and other growth and synthesis processes managed within the cleanroom operated by the Bruno Kessler Foundation (FBK). Ancillary techniques essential for fabrication are also discussed, along with the role of the FABLIMS software management system and a proposed ideal workflow designed to test the developed tools. The second part of the thesis introduces the NOMAD platform (Novel Materials Discovery), which serves as the destination environment for the FAIR data produced. Key features such as modular plugin deployment, schema packages, and the research application are presented in relation to their use within the project's context. Special attention is given to the taxonomy and ontology developed jointly by CNR-IFN (Trento) and CNR-ISMN (Bologna) to ensure consistent and interoperable data representation across all NFFA-DI laboratories. The final part focuses on the design and implementation of the "Fabrication-utilities" plugin, including an analysis of the repository structure, the rationale behind development choices, and the functionalities offered for structured data management. Potential improvements to the plugin are also discussed. The testing and performance evaluation of the developed tools are presented in the results chapter, with additional technical documentation provided in the appendices.

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Introduction

In the era of data-driven research and digital transformation, the effective management and responsible sharing of data have become central themes in both academia and industry. As organizations increasingly rely on large-scale, sensitive datasets to derive insights and drive innovation, there is a growing need for frameworks that ensure data is handled in a way that maximizes its value while maintaining security, privacy, and ethical standards.

The FAIR Data Principles—**Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**—were introduced in 2016 to address these challenges [1]. They provide a set of guidelines aimed at enhancing the discoverability, integration, and reuse of data assets for both human users and automated systems. At their core, the FAIR principles are not prescriptive rules but rather aspirational goals that guide the design and implementation of data management strategies. They encourage the use of rich metadata, standardized protocols, and community-endorsed vocabularies to maximize the value and impact of research data. By adhering to FAIR principles, data producers not only enhance the visibility and citation potential of their datasets but also contribute to a more open, transparent, and collaborative research ecosystem.

To introduce the key ideas guiding this thesis, the FAIR principles are summarized below. In [1], each principle is accompanied by a set of guiding rules to achieve the intended goals. In a non-exhaustive yet comprehensive manner, incorporating all the essential steps followed throughout this work, these goals are:

- **Findability:** Data should be as richly described as possible and associated with a persistent identifier (PID) such as a DOI, ensuring traceability. Additionally, both data and metadata must be registered and searchable.
- **Accessibility:** Open protocols should be explicitly used to retrieve digital resources via their identifiers, ensuring access for both humans

and machines. If access to protected data requires authorization, well-defined mechanisms should be in place. Furthermore, metadata should remain searchable even if the corresponding data is no longer available.

- **Interoperability:** Data and metadata should use formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable languages based on well-established ontologies and taxonomies. These should be linked to the data and metadata produced to ensure seamless integration and usability.
- **Reusability:** Data and metadata should contain all necessary information, including detailed provenance, and be released with a clearly defined usage license to facilitate reuse.

Originally developed to support open science and data sharing, the FAIR framework has since been adapted to a variety of contexts, including highly controlled and secure environments such as fabrication cleanrooms. These are critical infrastructures in the fabrication of advanced materials, sensors, microelectronics, and nanotechnology devices. They operate under stringent contamination control protocols and complex process monitoring systems. The complexity and sensitivity of operations carried out in cleanrooms generate vast amounts of data from process monitoring and environmental control to product quality inspection and lifecycle management.

Despite generating vast amounts of valuable process and equipment data, these laboratories often lack standardized and interoperable data management frameworks that align with FAIR principles [2]. As stated in [3], almost 38% of European universities lack research data management policies, and furthermore, it is not even on their current agendas. When focusing specifically on experimental and fabrication laboratories, the percentage is likely even lower. To address these gaps, dedicated data models and schema extensions are necessary to capture the unique metadata associated with fabrication steps, process parameters, and instrumentation. Many of these laboratories use proprietary software and data file formats, creating significant challenges for interoperability in fabrication processes.

Effectively managing and curating this data is essential not only for maintaining high production standards but also for enabling traceability, ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements, and supporting continuous improvement initiatives. In this context, the application of the FAIR data principles has become a central focus in scientific data management and curation, particularly within the European research landscape. To support open science practices, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) was established

as a global virtual environment where data from experimental and computational facilities are shared and made accessible to external users. Initiatives such as FAIRmat (FAIR Data Infrastructure for Condensed-Matter Physics and the Chemical Physics of Solids) are paving the way for the FAIRification of experimental data [4]. FAIRmat, part of the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), provides services and tools to assist in the curation and publication of FAIR-compliant datasets. However, the focus remains predominantly on characterization and simulation data rather than fabrication workflows. Nevertheless, a powerful tool for the FAIRification process, which is central to this thesis, is the NOMAD (Novel Materials Discovery) platform.

In this framework, efforts are also being made at the Italian level to comply with European requirements and guidelines. An outstanding example of the application of FAIR principles in fabrication laboratories is the NFFA-Digital Infrastructure (NFFA-DI) project [5], within which this work is developed. NFFA-DI is a major Italian initiative funded by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), aimed at creating a fully digitalized, distributed research infrastructure for nanoscience and nanotechnology. The infrastructure brings together eleven operational units across Italy, coordinated by the Italian National Research Council (CNR), integrating state-of-the-art clean-room facilities with advanced characterization techniques and computational resources.

A key feature of NFFA-DI is its FAIR-by-design approach to data management and curation. This strategy ensures that all research data—whether originating from fabrication processes, experimental characterizations, or computational simulations—is collected, described, and managed according to the FAIR principles, making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The core component of NFFA-DI’s data infrastructure is the Overarching FAIR Ecosystem for Data (OFED), which acts as a federated data lake. OFED integrates hardware resources (including high-performance computing nodes and storage solutions) with software services for metadata management, identity control, and automated data processing. Moreover, a repository, MinIO, was built to store all code, raw data, and other laboratory outputs from each unit. It is within this context that this thesis is written as the result of the Master in Data Management and Curation (MDMC) carried on from September 2024 to May 2025 between Trento and Trieste.

NFFA-DI’s commitment to FAIR data management reflects a broader European trend. However, while the FAIR guidelines are increasingly adopted

in computational and data-intensive domains, their implementation in experimental environments, such as cleanroom-based fabrication laboratories, remains at an early stage. This thesis focuses on applying FAIR data management principles to cleanroom processes, exploring strategies for data curation, standardization, and integration aimed at enhancing the quality and utility of production data in controlled manufacturing environments. To this end, and to comply with NFFA-DI requirements, the NOMAD platform from the FAIRmat group was used.

The Novel Materials Discovery (NOMAD) Laboratory [6] is one of the leading initiatives in materials science data management, providing a comprehensive infrastructure for storing, sharing, and analyzing data in accordance with FAIR principles. Developed as part of a European Centre of Excellence, NOMAD offers a robust ecosystem designed to support the entire data life-cycle in materials science from data generation and curation to publication and reuse.

At its core, NOMAD consists of several interconnected components:

- The NOMAD Repository, which serves as an open-access archive for materials science data, hosting millions of datasets contributed by researchers worldwide. It ensures data findability and accessibility, allowing users to upload, search, and retrieve data in standardized formats.
- The NOMAD Archive, which stores data in a normalized and processed form. This ensures interoperability, enabling data comparisons and analyses across different computational codes and experimental techniques.
- The NOMAD Metainfo (Metadata Infrastructure), which defines a flexible and extensible schema for describing materials data. This infrastructure forms the backbone for ensuring data reusability, providing rich metadata descriptions that capture both computational and experimental workflows.

One of the distinguishing features of NOMAD is its plugin system, which allows the community to extend the platform's capabilities by adding support for new data types, experimental methods, or computational workflows. Plugins in NOMAD are modular extensions that include parsers, schemas, and normalizers, enabling the integration of domain-specific knowledge and data standards into the platform. Through plugins, NOMAD can be adapted to cover emerging areas of research and evolving data requirements.

As part of this thesis work, an extension to the NOMAD Metainfo was developed through the implementation of a dedicated plugin designed to represent fabrication processes and the instruments used in cleanroom environments at CNR-IFN and the FBK Foundation in Trento. While NOMAD has traditionally focused on computational materials data and characterization techniques, the integration of manufacturing process data introduces new opportunities for holistic materials informatics—bridging the gap between material synthesis, processing, characterization, and application. The primary objectives are to enhance the traceability and reusability of data generated in cleanroom environments.

The work is organized as follows. Chapter 1 introduces the instrumentation and fabrication techniques cataloged at CNR-IFN Trento as part of the NFFA-DI project. It highlights the tools and processes made available to external users through the infrastructure’s integrated platform. Furthermore here the ideal data management pipeline envisioned for the cleanroom in Trento is provided, starting from the current practices adopted in Fablab Information Management Systems (FabLIMS). It details the test processes designed to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed workflows in capturing, managing, and curating fabrication data in accordance with FAIR principles. Chapter 2 provides an in-depth exploration of the NOMAD platform, focusing on its flexible schema definition capabilities and integrated search applications. In this chapter, the taxonomy collaboratively developed by the Trento and Bologna operational units is introduced, aiming to achieve cross-facility interoperability in cleanroom data management. Chapter 3 discusses the architecture of the plugin as implemented during the master. The results of the implementation, showcasing the visualization of curated data within the NOMAD environment and reflecting on the effectiveness of the adopted methodologies are presented in Chapter 4. This chapter also includes an outlook on future improvements and potential extensions to further enhance data interoperability and FAIR compliance in cleanroom contexts.

Finally, the appendices contain supplementary materials, including the source code of each metadata schema developed, scripts and configurations related to the NOMAD search application, and examples of the resulting JSON data structures generated from the standardized data ingestion processes. All code presented here and throughout this work can be found in the public GitHub repository: [FABRICATION-UTILITIES](#). Indeed, a fully FAIR-compliant data management pipeline should be built on open source code, except where security and privacy issues apply, following the ideal: "As open

as possible, as closed as necessary.

Chapter 1

Laboratory presentation

In this chapter, all the techniques listed in the NFFA-DI catalog for the laboratories located in Trento at CNR-IFN are presented. These laboratories include a cleanroom managed by the Bruno Kessler Foundation (FBK), which consists of three different rooms, each designed to be dedicated to specific operational steps. This separation aims to reduce environmental contamination caused by overlapping techniques, as some processes may leave more reaction residues than others.

The chapter is structured to provide an overview of each technique, accompanied, where available, by a graphical representation of the corresponding instrument. Additionally ancillary techniques, i.e. techniques that support the execution of primary process steps, are discussed where necessary, provided they are relevant to the following sections of this work. In the second part of this chapter, a brief description of the FABLIMS management system is provided. This ensures that all the foundational elements of the study are introduced. Finally, the chapter concludes with the presentation of an ideal workflow, intended as a test for the tools developed within this master's project. The results of the testing phase will be presented in Chapter 4.

1.1 NFFA-DI catalog

In presenting the NFFA-DI catalog for the Trento facilities, we will focus on growth and synthesis techniques while omitting characterization steps. This is because the main objective of this work is to create a FAIR-by-design environment for processes such as deposition, etching, and similar steps. The development of a FAIR environment for characterization was carried out by the characterization group. Therefore, in the following sections, we will

discuss only techniques and ancillary processes that are directly involved in fabrication, rather than measurement or analysis steps.

1.1.1 ICP CVD

Inductively Coupled Plasma Chemical Vapor Deposition (ICP CVD) is an advanced thin-film deposition technique that utilizes an inductively coupled plasma (ICP) source to enhance the dissociation of precursor gases, thereby improving film quality and deposition control at lower substrate temperatures. In our laboratory, we utilize the Oxford PlasmaPro 100 system for ICP CVD processes.

Figure 1.1: Oxford PlasmaPro 100

This tool features an advanced ICP source that provides a high-density plasma while maintaining low ion energy, minimizing substrate damage and enabling superior film quality. Additionally, the system allows precise control over process parameters, including gas flow rates, RF power levels, and substrate temperature, facilitating the deposition of high-quality dielectric and semiconductor films such as SiO₂, SiN_x, and diamond-like carbon. As depicted in Fig.1.2 the system comprises a lot of modules. Some as the control PC interfaces with a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) and a Control Rack, ensure automated process management, needed to export data to expose. The process gases are stored in the Gas Pod, which supplies reactant gases through a controlled delivery system. The gases are injected into the Process Chamber through controlled low lines (marked in magenta). The Vapour Delivery Module (VDM) provides also some additional precursor gases in vapor form, ensuring precise gas mixture control.

The system includes a Pumping Module to maintain the necessary vacuum conditions inside the Loadlock and Process Chamber, ensuring contamination-free processing. Plasma is generated thanks to the interplay of different component. The RF Generator/AMU (Automatic Matching Unit) generates high-frequency radio waves, which power the Upper Electrode inside the Process Chamber. This excites the process gases, creating a high-density Plasma (marked in green), which enhances the chemical reactions required for thin-film deposition. Additional RF Generators control ion

Figure 1.2: Schematic representation of the ICP CVD machine from Trento catalog.

energy, ensuring low-damage deposition.

The substrate is introduced through a Loadlock and transported via a Carrier into the Process Chamber, where it is positioned on a heated electrode. Vacuum levels, gas flows, and RF power are precisely regulated for optimized deposition conditions forming in the process the target material on the surface.

1.1.2 FIB

Available ion beam processes are direct writing by sputtering (milling), ion beam implantation and creation of defects to locally modify material properties, ion beam induced deposition of materials exploiting the presence of gas injection systems (GIS). Besides imaging, available electron beam processes are electron beam lithography and electron beam induced material depositions exploiting the GIS tools.

The samples are loaded on a laser interferometer controlled stage that allows nanometric step size in both x and y directions and ensures a precise control of the position. This enables nanometric alignments to previously present

Figure 1.3: FIB-SEM instrument a Trento: RAITH VELION

markers (mix and match lithography) or ‘blind-navigation’ with excellent stitching performance among different writing fields. The operator loads the samples and sets the beam parameters. After optimizing the beams it is possible to load a layout (CAD file) and the system will start executing the patterning process. The system can provide focused beams of Si, Au and Ge ions, with energy up to $70keV$ (for double-charged ions). The ion column (FIB) normal to sample surface combined with the precise positioning of the stage thanks to the laser interferometric stage, makes this tool useful for nanofabrication.

1.1.3 EBL

EBL is a direct write patterning process that uses a focused, concentrated stream of electrons to modify the solubility of a resist layer. Electron-beam lithography (often abbreviated as e-beam lithography or EBL) is the practice of scanning a focused beam of electrons to draw custom shapes on a surface covered with an electron-sensitive film called a resist (exposing). The electron beam changes the solubility of the resist, enabling selective removal of either the exposed or non-exposed regions of the resist by immersing it in a solvent (developing).

The purpose, as with photolithography, is to create very small structures in the resist that can subsequently be transferred to the substrate material,

often by etching. The primary advantage of electron-beam lithography is that it can draw custom patterns (direct-write) with sub-10nm resolution. This form of maskless lithography has high resolution but low throughput, limiting its usage to photomask fabrication, low-volume production of semiconductor devices, and research and development.

Figure 1.4: EBL Tescan Nisaba at FBK

This instrument requires a resist layer and involves two main ancillary techniques: a spin coating step, to deposit the resist, and a development step. The latter doesn't require much explanation, as it simply involves exposing the material to a chemical agent that modifies its properties. A resist can be developed in either a positive or negative tone, or it can be used for a lift-off process. In any case, the main features are similar, so there are not many differences to discuss.

As for the spin coating step, it involves depositing a layer of resist using a spinner. Additionally, various thermal processes can be carried out to harden the resist. Primers may also be used to improve adhesion between the resist and the substrate. Overall, it involves a large number of parameters.

1.1.4 ICP-RIE

Inductively Coupled Plasma Reactive Ion Etching (ICP-RIE) is an advanced dry etching technique that combines both physical sputtering and chemical reactions to achieve high-resolution, anisotropic etch profiles. In this process, a plasma is generated in a low-pressure environment using an inductively coupled electromagnetic field, which ionizes a reactive gas mixture. The system features two independently controlled power sources: a high-frequency RF source driving the inductive coil to sustain a high-density plasma, and a separate RF bias applied to the substrate electrode to control ion energy and directionality.

In the ICP-RIE configuration, such as in the Oxford PlasmaPro Cobra 300, energy is coupled into the plasma through a coil located around the cham-

Figure 1.5: ICP-RIE system at Trento: PlasmaPro100 Cobra 300

ber, enabling high plasma densities ($> 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) at relatively low operating pressures (typically $1 - 10 \text{ mTorr}$). This allows for enhanced ionization efficiency and better control over etch profiles and selectivity. The Cobra 300 system features a modular and flexible design, allowing for precise control of critical process parameters, including coil power, platen power (substrate bias), gas flow rates, chamber pressure, and temperature.

During operation, reactive species (such as radicals and ions) are generated from input gases. These ions are accelerated toward the substrate under the influence of the substrate bias, facilitating both physical bombardment and chemical etching of the material. The combination of high-density plasma and independent ion energy control enables highly anisotropic etching, essential for pattern transfer in nanofabrication and advanced microelectronics.

The Oxford PlasmaPro Cobra 300 is particularly suited for the etching of dielectric materials, including *polySi*, SiO_2 , and Si_3N_4 , and features fine-tuned endpoint detection using an integrated optical emission spectrometer (Ocean Optics). The versatility and process stability of this dry etch tool makes it an indispensable tool for research and development in semiconductor device fabrication.

1.2 FABLIMS

As already mentioned the laboratories are hosted in the FBK foundation. It is well recognized in two main scientific areas: AI and silicon sensors. A dedicated Facility, in FBK, includes more than 1500 sqm of laboratories with cleanrooms for sensor fabrication, dicing and packaging setups, characterization tools. So tents of users accessing the facility every day and hundreds of wafers running around among the cleanrooms require dedicated organization and tools to guarantee results, quality, tracking, safety. Since 1995, FBK Facility invested to have a LIMS to manage all of that, and in 2021 the new LIMS, FabLIMS, was deployed.

FabLIMS is the LIMS, Laboratory Information Management System, designed and implemented to manage research activities in the laboratories of the Fondazione Bruno Kessler. This software manages all the laboratories, all the projects and connect samples and wafers tracking all operations they are involved in. Among main functions: user management, equipment management, equipment booking, process flow design and tracking, SPC, material characterization, accountability. The FBK Facility is certified 9001-2015, and most of the information yearly examined by the ISO auditors are managed in FabLIMS.

Thanks to its architecture, FabLIMS is extremely flexible, allowing users to add equipment, activity types, recipes, permissions. On the other hand, it allows to group people to carefully manage IP, and to guarantee visibility of technology details only where needed. FabLIMS is a web oriented platform, which allow to access it from wherever, inside a specific network, and this is of overarching importance since allow to researchers and cleanroom staff to easily share and update information about wafer processing, with no need to always stay in the same laboratory. Furthermore, storing the processes guarantee to keep the know-how in structured and standardized way, even in case of retirements or other situation with people leaving from FBK.

There are also advanced functions, like the possibility to specify materials which are forbidden in some equipment, because of contamination risks, and the specification of what type of items, samples can be handled by each equipment. These last features are extremely important to know in advance if a certain type of samples could be processed or not in the FBK labs. Recently, a function dedicated to “non conformities” management has been activated, with sections for NCs for equipment, processes, safety. Thanks to its flexible architecture, FabLIMS starts to be a reference LIMS platform even

outside FBK. In NFFA-DI it has been chosen to manage data and metadata of equipment and experiments referring to the research activity performed in the FBK cleanrooms in support to CNR-IFN@TN. All the equipment available in the NFFA-DI catalogue installed in the FBK cleanrooms are managed with FabLIMS. Furthermore, A common vocabulary/taxonomy for describing cleanroom process flows has been agreed between CNR-IFN@TN, FBK and CNR-ISM Bologna and it has been integrated in FabLIMS.

1.3 Ideal processes for testing

To test the ideal pipeline in which the plugin presented in the next two chapters is employed, we chose a process consisting of five steps, which can be summarized as follows:

- 1) A coating step to deposit a photoresist material in preparation for a subsequent lithography step;
- 2) The lithography step, performed through an Electron Beam Lithography (EBL) procedure;
- 3) After lithography, the resist is patterned through a developing step;
- 4) To improve the functionality of the resist, a baking step is performed to harden the resist and enhance its quality;
- 5) Finally, a Reactive Ion Etching (RIE) procedure, specifically an Inductively Coupled Plasma RIE (ICP-RIE), is performed to etch and define the final pattern of the process.

The parameters set throughout the process are presented for each step in the following tables: "As can be seen by the rest of the work, these parameters

Parameter [unit]	Value
Spin frequency [rpm]	4000
Resist name [-]	AR-P 6200.09

Table 1.1: Parameters for the coating step

represent only a portion of the total parameters available in a cleanroom process. However, in the approach presented in the following chapters, more and more parameters are included. Here, the focus is solely on the pipeline and its automation test.

Parameter [unit]	Value
Tension [kV]	30
Current [pA]	70
Writing field dimension [μm]	100
Dose [$\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$]	100
Address size [nm]	7
Alignment required [-]	True

Table 1.2: Parameters for the EBL step

Parameter [unit]	Value
Developing solution [-]	AR_600.546
Developing time [s]	60
Developing temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	20
Stopping solution [-]	IPA
Stopping time [s]	30
Cleaning solution [-]	DIH ₂ O
Cleaning time [s]	30

Table 1.3: Parameters for the developing step

Parameter [unit]	Value
Chuck temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	130

Table 1.4: Parameters for the baking step

Parameter [unit]	Value
Target material [-]	Poly-Si
Depth target [nm]	200
Duration target [min]	1
Etching rate target [-]	260
SF6 flow [sccm]	16
CHF3 flow [sccm]	73

Table 1.5: Parameters for the ICP-RIE step

Chapter 2

Nomad and plugin pre-production

This chapter is devoted to present the fundamental tools and pre-production steps that will be useful throughout the rest of this thesis. In particular, the first part of the chapter introduces the NOMAD environment, to which data are sent. NOMAD (Novel Materials Discovery) is a comprehensive, open-source platform designed to facilitate FAIR data management in materials science. It enables researchers to store, process, and share scientific data efficiently, ensuring reproducibility and accessibility across different studies and disciplines. Specifically, we will explore the key features that will be further developed and analyzed in this work: modularity and plugin deployment, schema packages, and the research app. In the second part, we will present the taxonomy adopted for data representation. To ensure interoperability, the ontologies and taxonomies used to structure data should be widely recognized within the scientific community. Therefore, the taxonomy presented here—developed through the collaboration of CNR-IFN in Trento and CNR-ISMN in Bologna—aims to be adopted across all NFFA-DI laboratories and other cleanroom facilities.

2.1 Nomad

NOMAD organizes data hierarchically, similar to a file system. Each dataset consists of multiple entries, which represent the fundamental data units within the platform. These entries contain raw data files and metadata that provide context and traceability, helping users understand the origin and significance of the data. The entries are uploaded to a specific section of the NOMAD interface, ensuring structured data management and accessibility. The system ensures consistency by defining each section with specific attributes such as names, descriptions, types, units, and shapes, enhancing

(a) General uploads page. In red, the button to initialize a new upload, and in green, the PIDs generated by NOMAD for each upload.

(b) General aspects of an upload. In blue, the button to upload a file, to which an ID is linked.

(c) When navigating within an upload, the files section is visible. Here, files can be pre-viewed or included as processed data if an archive.json file is created.

(d) On the left, the structure of a general parsed archive is displayed, while on the right, the processed data is shown.

Figure 2.1: General features of the NOMAD interface for uploads and data visualization.

machine-readability and facilitating advanced searches and analyses. Once data is uploaded to NOMAD, it undergoes a structured processing pipeline:

- **Parsing** – Extracting and structuring information from raw scientific files. NOMAD supports various file formats, allowing seamless integration with different research workflows.
- **Normalization** – Refining extracted data to ensure consistency, accuracy, and compliance with established scientific standards.

This processing pipeline allows researchers to work with well-structured and normalized datasets, making the data suitable for further analysis, visualization, and reuse.

NOMAD operates as a modern web-based application designed with scalability and efficiency in mind. It consists of two main components:

- **App** – Manages the user interface, API, and documentation, providing an intuitive experience for researchers.
- **Worker** – Executes data processing tasks such as parsing and normalizing data, ensuring that uploaded data is correctly structured.

This modern architecture allows users to easily develop custom NOMAD plugins to adapt local instances of NOMAD, like its development distribution and [OASIS](#). We will discuss plugins in more detail shortly, but for now, it is important to highlight that NOMAD can be customized using YAML (Yet Another Markup Language, also known as YAML Ain't Markup Language) files. However, for more advanced and flexible customization, NOMAD can be modified directly through Python (.py) files, allowing users to extend its already rich environment.

In our work, given the available possibilities, we chose to work directly in Python. However, for the sake of clarity, a possible YAML file (the complete extension must be name.archive.yaml) for an upload configuration is in [1](#). Despite the unfamiliar syntax and glossary used in the example, if we upload this kind of file "name_file.archive.yaml" in NOMAD, we will see Etcher and Massflow Controller as custom entities. i.e. available to be processed to form a schema. However, as previously stated, YAML files will not be used in the remainder of this work.

Raw data processed in NOMAD is stored in entities called EntryArchive.

```
definitions:
  name: 'Etching workflow schema'
  sections:
    Etcher:
      base_sections:
        - nomad.datamodel.metainfo.eln.Instrument
        - nomad.datamodel.data.EntryData
      quantities:
        capabilities:
          type: str
        m_annotations:
          eln:
            component: StringEditQuantity
    Massflow_controller:
      base_sections:
        - nomad.datamodel.metainfo.eln.Chemical
        - nomad.datamodel.data.EntryData
      m_annotations:
        eln:
          overview: True
          hide: ['lab_id', 'datetime', 'description']
      quantities:
        massflow:
          type: np.float64
          unit: centimeter^3/minute
          m_annotations:
            eln:
              component: NumberEditQuantity
              defaultDisplayUnit: centimeter^3/minute
```

Listing 1: Example of YAML file to customize NOMAD.

This is a Python class defined in the NOMAD repository and forms the core of every NOMAD instance. An `EntryArchive` contains fundamental information, such as the `"entry_id"`, which serves as the PID (Persistent Identifier) for each upload, along with other essential metadata. Additionally, each archive built in NOMAD is saved in JSON format and is assigned a specific file extension: `"file_name.archive.json"`.

Furthermore, for an `EntryArchive` to be fully readable, it must inherit from two fundamental data model classes: `EntryData` and `ArchiveSection`. Using these classes allows the interface to be populated and data to be saved, while also automatically enriching metadata that NOMAD generates upon upload. Overall, a standard processed dataset in NOMAD appears as structured in Figure 2.1, with three main sections:

- **Results** Contains a summary of key values within the entries. This section is particularly useful for simulation uploads, but in the context of this work, it does not play a crucial role.
- **Metadata** Includes all automatically generated information within NOMAD, which is essential for data contextualization. This section is particularly relevant in a FAIR-compliant environment, supporting findability and reusability.
- **Data** Contains the processed data necessary to understand the process described in the upload.

To provide a more complete picture, NOMAD is organized at a higher level into a Section-Subsection structure. When defining a Section, it is possible to nest Subsections at any depth. In general, sections are composed of elements called "Quantities", which are Python classes defined in NOMAD that support a wide range of data types, including strings, numbers, files, and datetime values.

Each available section type in NOMAD is stored in the `metainfo` repository and can be recalled when needed. A particularly useful category of sections is `BaseSections`, which provide a flexible way to describe data. Below are some `BaseSections` that will be used throughout this work:

- **ElementalComposition** As the name suggests, this section allows the description of the elemental composition of a chemical compound, which may be used as a substrate or a reactive species.

- **ProcessStep** A core base class in NOMAD that enables the description of any processing step performed on an item or sample. In this work, it will serve as the foundation for creating a custom "Fabrication-ProcessStep", which contains additional data relevant to fabrication procedures (Chapter 3).
- **Process** In NOMAD, a process is defined as "a planned operation that results in physical changes to a specified input material." This BaseSection allows for detailed chronological data and can contain multiple ProcessStep entries to describe the complete processing history of a sample. Additionally, NOMAD provides a Workflow section, which supplements the three main sections by enabling the reconstruction and graphical representation of the entire process.

As previously mentioned, once a Section is defined in NOMAD, it can be nested through the Subsection mechanism at any level. Another key feature of NOMAD is the ability to inherit properties from an existing class. At the Python level, this inheritance is implemented directly in class definitions, allowing developers to extend and customize previously defined classes as a starting point for new ones.

A fundamental feature of NOMAD is the availability of ELNs (Electronic Lab Notebooks). For these, several base classes are defined in the metainfo repository, which are both callable and inheritable. The fundamental ELN base classes used in this work are:

- **Instrument** A very basic class used to describe and associate an ID with any type of instrument used in a process.
- **Chemical** This class describes any type of chemical, providing a name, a description, and, most importantly, a chemical formula. In this work, each chemical is linked to a repetitive subsection called ElementalComposition, ensuring a fully findable and reusable environment, as will be demonstrated later.

These were the main features of NOMAD and the minimum set required for the rest of this thesis. However, for further details, a comprehensive and well-structured documentation is available at: [NOMAD Documentation](#).

The NOMAD plugin system allows users to customize and extend the platform's functionalities by integrating external Python packages. These plugins function as modular components, adding new capabilities without modifying

the core NOMAD software. A NOMAD plugin is a Python package that contains multiple entry points, defining the functionalities it provides. Plugins enable users to define their own schemas to represent data, create new parsers to read specific file formats that need to be uploaded on the platform, develop normalizers to apply custom processing actions on the data and implement apps that enhance searchability for the data stored in a schema. Each of these features has its own entry point, specified in the pyproject.toml file. An example of an entry point declaration is: Each entry point corresponds

```
[project.entry-points.'nomad.plugin']
schema_package_entry_point =
↪ "fabrication_facilities.schema_packages: schema_package_entry_point"
```

Listing 2: Example of pyproject.toml entry point

to a Python class defined for customization in the respective "init.py" file. In the previous example, we would expect to find a structure like this in the fabrication_facilities.schema_packages directory:

```
1 from nomad.config.models.plugins import SchemaPackageEntryPoint
2
3
4 class ItemsEntryPoint(SchemaPackageEntryPoint):
5     def load(self):
6         from fabrication_facilities.schema_packages.Items import m_package
7
8         return m_package
9
10
11 Items_entry_point = ItemsEntryPoint(
12     name='FabricationItems',
13     description='Schema package for describing items in fabrications.',
14 )
15
16
17 class UtilitiesEntryPoint(SchemaPackageEntryPoint):
```

To build the plugin we followed these steps:

- Cloned the template from the [NOMAD plugin template repository](#). This provided access to powerful tools like Cruft, which automates the creation of the plugin's basic structure and associates metadata with it.
- Implemented the required features. In our case, we used only schema packages and app functionalities, following NOMAD's standard method for writing JSON files. Thus, no custom parsers were needed. However, we included a normalizer, which, although not yet developed, could be expanded in future upgrades.

Once all these steps are completed, the plugin can be uploaded to a local instance of NOMAD. If the local instance is a development distribution, the plugin can be used as a submodule. However, if the instance is an OASIS distribution, a Docker image must be created to integrate the plugin. For the purpose of this work, in the following sections, we will delve deeper into schema packages and apps. However first let us present briefly a feature crucial for the uploading of the schemas adopted in Chapter 3: the APIs in Nomad.

In the context of the NOMAD platform, the API (Application Programming Interface) system enables the extension and integration of new functionalities during an upload. NOMAD allows developers to create custom APIs using FastAPI, a modern Python framework for building high-performance web services. The integration is achieved through an API entry point, defined in the `APIEntryPoint` class, where the `load` method returns a FastAPI application configured with the necessary routes and middleware. To ensure proper registration of the new API within the system, the entry point must be declared in the `pyproject.toml` configuration file of the plugin. This setup allows various actions to be performed during an upload, such as ensuring the correct ordering of uploaded files or implementing other crucial features.

2.1.1 Schema packages

Schema packages, which are collections of metadata definitions that describe complex data structures and workflows, form the semantic framework that supports advanced data curation and search functionalities within the platform. They allow researchers to represent data in a consistent, machine-readable format, facilitating interoperability and data reuse. To create a schema package, the plugin directory should follow this minimal structure: In this structure, the "init.py" file could contain the previously mentioned

```
plugin/  
|-- src/  
    |-- plugin_example/  
        |-- schema_packages/  
            |-- __init__.py  
            |-- myschema.py  
            |-- schema_package.py  
        |-- __init__.py  
    |-- LICENSE.txt  
    |-- pyproject.toml
```

Listing 3: Minimal tree for a schema packages plugin.

entry points, while `myschema.py` defines the schemas used in the plugin. The `pyproject.toml` file includes all the necessary entry points for local uploads.

Going a bit deeper into the definition of a NOMAD schema, the `myschema.py` file includes a structure similar to the following:

```
from nomad.datamodel.data import (
    ArchiveSection,
    EntryData
)
from nomad.metainfo import (
    Quantity,
    SubSection,
    Package
)

m_package = Package(name='Example schema')

class AnotherSection(ArchiveSection):

class MySchema(ArchiveSection, EntryData):
    my_quantity = Quantity(
        type=str,
        description='Una descrizione della mia quantità.'
    )

    my_subsection = SubSection(
        sub_section=AnotherSection,
        repeats=True
    )
    def normalize(self, archive, logger):
        super().normalize(archive, logger)

    #instructions

m_package.__init_metainfo__()
```

With this setup, `MySchema` is recognized as a built-in schema in NOMAD, thanks to its inheritance from `EntryData`. Additionally, we include `ArchiveSection` for completeness, as `EntryData` already inherits from it. However, not all schemas need to be part of the built-in schemas (overpopulating the system can hinder visualization). In such cases, using `ArchiveSection` as a standalone component allows schemas to be used in a `SubSection` instead.

Furthermore, this example demonstrates the nesting of sections. The `"repeats=True"` option allows a subsection to be repeated, generating a list of `AnotherSection` type subsections. One of the most powerful features shown here is the `normalize` function. This function, while highly customizable depending on its specific purpose, enables various operations on data. In the provided example, it is used primarily for autofilling fields, but its applications are vast, making it a crucial tool for enhancing data consistency and

```
plugin/  
|-- src/  
    |-- plugin_example/  
        |-- apps/  
            |-- __init__.py  
            |-- __init__.py  
|-- LICENSE.txt  
|-- pyproject.toml
```

Listing 4: Minimal tree for an apps plugin.

automation within NOMAD.

2.1.2 Apps

Another key element of the NOMAD ecosystem is its Apps Framework, which provides interactive web applications for data visualization, analysis, and exploration. These apps enable users to perform advanced queries, visualize materials properties, and analyze datasets directly within the NOMAD environment, without the need for external tools. Customizing a research app allows for full FAIR compliance, at least in terms of ensuring the findability and reusability of every object and entry used to describe a dataset. Within the plugin repository, research apps are typically structured as follows: Where in the "init.py" file in apps it is possible to find something like:

```
from nomad.config.models.plugins import AppEntryPoint  
  
from nomad.config.models.ui import (  
    App,  
    Column,  
    Menu,  
    MenuItemCustomQuantities,  
    SearchQuantities,  
    Axis,  
    Menu,  
    MenuItemHistogram,  
    MenuItemPeriodicTable,  
    MenuItemTerms,  
)  
  
exampleapp = App(  
    label='Example',  
    path='pathtoapp',  
    category='Useful category',  
    description='Short description',  
    readme="""  
        A way longer description  
        """,  
    search_quantities=SearchQuantities(  
        include=['*#path/to/the/schemas/to/include'],  
    ),  
    columns=[  
        Column(quantity='entry_name', selected=True),
```

```

    Column(quantity='entry_type'),
    Column(quantity='upload_create_time', selected=True),
  ],
  filters_locked={'section_defs.definition_qualified_name': 'path/to/the/schemas/to/lock'},
  menu=Menu(
    items=[
      MenuItemTerms(
        title='First quantity',
        type='terms',
        search_quantity={'data.firstquantity#path/to/the/quantity/to/search'},
      ),
      Menu(
        title='A nested menu',
        indentation=0,
        items=[
          MenuItemHistogram(
            title='A numerical quantity',
            type='histogram',
            n_bins=10,
            x=Axis(
              search_quantity='data.quantity#path/to/the/quantity/to/search',
              title='a title for the axis',
              unit='unit',
            ),
          ),
        ],
      ),
    ],
  ),
),
),
)

equipment_app_entry_point = AppEntryPoint(
  name='Fabrication_equipment_search',
  description='New app for equipment of fabrication facilities.',
  app=equipmentapp,
)

```

The fundamental components of a NOMAD app are menus, which contain the filters used for performing searches. Filters, called items, come in a variety of types, with the most common being "menuItemTerms" that allow to search string and boolean and "menuItemHistogram" used for all numerical values (e.g., integers, floating-point numbers, and datetime values), offering both search capabilities and graphical visualization. Menus can be nested at arbitrary levels, allowing for hierarchical filtering structures. They also contain several specific fields that enhance the user interface visualization. A crucial limitation to note is that NOMAD can currently search only scalar quantities, and this constraint is accounted for in the app's design.

Another essential feature of a NOMAD app is that only the quantities and schemas included in the "search_quantities" field are indexed for searching. This means that users must explicitly define which schemas and quantities should be searchable. Once a search is performed, the results are displayed in the interface through the columns section of the app. These columns rep-

resent the key quantities used to present search results and are divided into native quantities standard quantities that do not require specifying a path within the dataset's data section and customized quantities, user-defined quantities, typically introduced through plugin schemas (such as the one we will define in our case).

Several additional features further enhance the functionality of research apps. A "filters_locked" voice allows the application of invisible filters, which can restrict searches to a specific subset of entries without users being aware of the filtering process. Widgets provide a visually appealing and practical way to present filters directly within the columns space. Although we will not use this option, users can still temporarily enable widgets within the research app if needed. As previously mentioned, apps and schemas will be explored in greater detail in the following chapter. The general concepts introduced here will be expanded upon in Chapter 3, with more in-depth explanations and practical examples.

2.2 Taxonomy and vocabulary adopted

At this stage, it is essential to introduce the taxonomy adopted as a guiding framework for plugin development. Interoperability is a fundamental principle in the FAIR-by-design approach, relying on ontologies, dictionaries, and standardized vocabularies to ensure seamless data integration. Consequently, the taxonomy presented here is specifically designed for fabrication realities, as developed through the collaborative efforts of the NFFA-DI nodes of Bologna and Trento [7]. This marks a significant step toward a holistic and comprehensive description of cleanroom environments, with the potential for future expansion to include all NFFA-DI nodes.

As with all taxonomies and ontologies, this framework is based on existing material science standards, specifically ISO/TS 80004 and ISO 16684 2015, which provide a standardized vocabulary for describing fabrication processes. Additionally, this taxonomy synthesizes process descriptions from the data management software FABLIMS and CAMS (the respective of FABLIMS in Bologna). In FABLISM steps and ancillary sub-steps are treated as distinct entities. For instance, in lithography, the development stage is considered a separate step rather than an inherent part of the overall process. This distinction is reflected in the taxonomy's process descriptions. This model introduces a branching system based on hierarchical classifications: super-classes, i.e. Broad categories representing groups of fabrication steps that

induce the same type of modification on the material (e.g., ADD, REMOVE, TRANSFORM), they are divided in process class, i.e. more specific categories such as lithography, etching, bonding, integration, synthesis, dicing, doping, solution modification, thermal processing, and labeling and the most granular level, detailing individual techniques, such as ICP CVD, DRIE, FIB, EBL, etc. For completeness, the taxonomy also includes a Characterization superclass; however, this aspect is not extended in the present work, as this thesis focuses solely on fabrication, for more detail you can see [7]. Furthermore, many characterization processes are already well-integrated within NOMAD, benefiting from standardized frameworks such as NeXus. As a result, incorporating characterization into this taxonomy in the future would require only minimal adjustments.

Chapter 3

Plugin

In this chapter, we present the architecture of the plugin as implemented in the Git repository: [Fabrication-utilities](#). We begin by providing essential information to facilitate easy navigation through the repository's directories and to understand the underlying structure of the plugin. Additionally, we will discuss the design choices made during development, highlighting why specific solutions were preferred over others. The core functional components of the plugin are divided into two main sections schema packages, defining the data structure for various fabrication steps, in the first part and of the research apps, implementing search functionalities for structured data retrieval, in the second. Throughout this chapter, visual representations of the code will be provided to enhance understanding. Furthermore, potential improvements to the existing implementation will be briefly discussed. The performance evaluation of the plugin will be addressed in the following Chapter 4. Additionally, more extensive code documentation, particularly concerning the schema structure for the fabrication steps in the NFFA-DI project (Trento facility), will be provided in Appendix A.

3.1 General structure

The plugin was developed using the template repository provided by the FAIRmat group, accessible at the following link: [NOMAD plugin template repository](#). This repository offers a powerful tool, Cruft, which facilitates the creation of a structured skeleton for a NOMAD plugin. It ensures that all necessary metadata for code findability and reusability are included. Additionally, it allows users to select a license for the plugin's distribution.

We choose a BSD-3 (Berkeley Software Distribution 3-Clause) License [8]

which is a permissive open-source license that allows software to be freely used, modified, and distributed, while still providing proper attribution to the original authors. Unlike more restrictive licenses (such as the GPL), the BSD-3 license imposes minimal obligations on users, making it highly compatible with both open-source and proprietary projects.

Furthermore, the template repository integrates Cruft with the Cookiecutter Python package, which helps maintain the plugin up to date. Once the initial plugin structure was generated, the final repository organization was structured as illustrated in List 5. As visible, the plugin also includes a nor-

```
FABRICATION-UTILITIES/  
|-- .devcontainer  
|-- .github  
|-- .vscode  
|-- docs/  
|-- src/  
    |-- fabrication_facilities/  
        |-- apps/  
            |-- __init__.py  
            |-- directories.py  
            |-- equipmentapp.py  
            |-- menu_steps.py  
            |-- processapp.py  
            |-- stepapp.py  
        |-- normalizers/  
        |-- schema_packages/  
            |-- __init__.py  
            |-- add.py  
            |-- fabrication_utilities.py  
            |-- Items.py  
            |-- remove.py  
            |-- transform.py  
            |-- utils.py  
    |-- __init__.py  
|-- tests  
|-- .cruft.json  
|-- .gitignore  
|-- MANIFEST.in  
|-- requirements_docs.txt  
|-- LICENSE.txt  
|-- pyproject.toml
```

Listing 5: Structure of the plugin developed.

malizers submodule, although no specific implementations are present yet. However, its inclusion is intended to support potential future decisions to introduce ad hoc data operations, making the presence of a normalizer module necessary. Conversely, no parsers are included in this implementation. This is due to two main reasons: the decision to use NOMAD’s JSON structure for data uploads, eliminating the need for dedicated parsers and avoiding the

rigidity of a method designed to read only specific file types, thereby allowing future users to manually populate the NOMAD entries created through the schemas. Additionally, users have the flexibility to extend the plugin by defining their own parsers, either by forking or cloning the repository.

As previously mentioned, the plugin is licensed under BSD-3-Clause, with the license details provided in the LICENSE.txt file. This was made possible thanks to the Cruft feature. Furthermore, all necessary entry points required for the plugin's functionality have been included in pyproject.toml. The "fabrication_facilities" directory, which constitutes the core of the plugin. Other elements in the main branch of the repository serve as supporting components for Git workspace management and related procedures. Files such as requirements.txt list essential Python packages that facilitate development and are installed upon plugin deployment.

3.2 Schemas

Let us now focus on schemas. The schema packages are defined within the homonymous subdirectory. Here, the structure of each entry point is specified in the "init.py" file, where all schema entry points are created. Each entry point is linked to a file whose defined entries should be made visible in NOMAD. For instance, the main entry point related to the core schema package module has the form:

```
from nomad.config.models.plugins import SchemaPackageEntryPoint

class UtilitiesEntryPoint(SchemaPackageEntryPoint):
    def load(self):
        from fabrication_facilities.schema_packages.fabrication_utilities import (
            m_package,
        )

        return m_package

Utilities_entry_point = UtilitiesEntryPoint(
    name='FabricationEquipments&Steps',
    description='Schema package for describing equipments and steps in fabrication.',
)
```

The file utils.py contains several utility classes and functions used throughout the project. It serves as a support module that can be expanded in the future. Currently, it contains two key components. The first is the function "parse_chemical_formula" implemented as follows:

```
28 def parse_chemical_formula(formula):
```

```

29 formula = formula.replace('.', '.')
30 if '.' in formula:
31     main_part, hydrate_part = formula.split('.')
32 else:
33     main_part, hydrate_part = formula, None
34
35 def extract_elements(compound):
36     # Espressione per trovare elementi chimici seguiti da un numero opzionale
37     matches = re.findall(r'([A-Z][a-z]*)(\d*)', compound)
38     elements = defaultdict(int)
39
40     for element, count in matches:
41         elements[element] += int(count) if count else 1
42
43     return elements
44
45 element_main = defaultdict(int)
46
47 # Espandiamo le parentesi prima di estrarre gli elementi
48 while '(' in main_part:
49     main_part = re.sub(
50         r'\(([\^()]*)\)(\d+)', lambda m: m.group(1) * int(m.group(2)), main_part
51     )
52
53 # Trova elementi e numeri
54 matches = re.findall(r'([A-Z][a-z]*)(\d*)', main_part)
55
56 for element, count in matches:
57     element_main[element] += (
58         int(count) if count else 1
59     ) # Se il numero manca, assume 1
60
61 if hydrate_part:
62     hydrate_match = re.match(r'(\d*)H2O', hydrate_part)
63     if hydrate_match:
64         water_molecules = (
65             int(hydrate_match.group(1)) if hydrate_match.group(1) else 1
66         )
67         elements_hydrate = extract_elements('H2O')
68
69         for element, count in elements_hydrate.items():
70             element_main[element] += count * water_molecules
71
72 # Convertiamo il dizionario in due liste ordinate
73 elements = list(element_main.keys())
74 counts = list(element_main.values())
75
76 return elements, counts

```

This function leverages the python packages `re` and `collections`. The former enables the use of regular expressions to extract chemical elements and their quantities from a string formula, while the latter helps structure the data into a dictionary-like format using elements as keys and their counts as values, initializing missing keys automatically to prevent errors. Currently, the performance of this function is quite good, successfully parsing a wide variety of simple compounds used in fabrication processes, including hydrates and complex organic compounds with nested groups. However, charged compounds are not yet supported.

The second component is the class "Massflow_controller", used to describe fluximeters employed in fabrication processes such as RIE and others:

```

79 class Massflow_controller(Chemical, ArchiveSection):
80     """
81     Class autogenerated from yaml schema.
82     """
83
84     m_def = Section(
85         a_eln={'overview': True, 'hide': ['lab_id', 'datetime']},
86     )
87     massflow = Quantity(
88         type=np.float64,
89         description='Rate at which the gas flows',
90         a_eln={
91             'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
92             'defaultDisplayUnit': 'centimeter^3/minute',
93         },
94         unit='centimeter^3/minute',
95     )
96
97     elemental_composition = SubSection(
98         section_def=ElementalComposition,
99         repeats=True,
100    )
101
102    def normalize(self, archive: 'EntryArchive', logger: 'BoundLogger') -> None:
103        super().normalize(archive, logger)
104        if self.chemical_formula:
105            elements, counts = parse_chemical_formula(self.chemical_formula)
106            total = 0
107            for token in counts:
108                total += int(token)
109            mass = sum(am[an[el]] * cou for el, cou in zip(elements, counts))
110            if total != 0:
111                elemental_fraction = np.array(counts) / total
112                elementality = []
113                i = 0
114                for entry in elements:
115                    elemental_try = ElementalComposition()
116                    elemental_try.element = entry
117                    elemental_try.atomic_fraction = elemental_fraction[i]
118                    mass_frac = (am[an[entry]] * counts[i]) / mass
119                    elemental_try.mass_fraction = mass_frac
120                    i += 1
121                    elementality.append(elemental_try)
122            else:
123                print('No elements provided')
124            self.elemental_composition = elementality

```

This class provides a good example of NOMAD's structural logic. For instance, the use of the "Chemical" allows a proper description of the chemical species flowing through the controller, while the ArchiveSection inheritance is required to use the class as a SubSection in other schemas. Another important element is the use of annotations via "a_eln", which enables customization of the ELN (Electronic Lab Notebook) view. This includes hiding specific fields (hide command), setting the display order, and defining

interactions or constraints on the data shown.

The main feature of the class is its `normalize` method, which automatically fills the list of `ElementalComposition` subsections by using the function defined `"parse_chemical_formula"`. The method parses the provided chemical formula and generates two corresponding lists: one for the elements and one for their respective counts. It then uses these to populate the subsections iteratively. For accessing chemical and physical properties of the elements, the class relies on the `ASE` package, specifically the `ase.data` submodule, which offers a powerful database for material scientists and chemists. This workflow is reused in all classes where chemical formulas are a key component of the data structure.

The main logic of the plugin is implemented in the `"fabrication_utilities.py"` file. Here, a broad set of classes is defined, beginning with a series of classes representing the taxonomy introduced in [Sec.2.2](#). These classes are then used to describe each technique available across cleanroom equipment. For completeness, the plugin also includes preliminary support for tracking items and their registrations, through the class `SampleParenting`. However, this feature is still under development and thus is not covered in depth in this work.

In the remainder of this section, we will delve deeper into the plugin's most mature features: the description of equipment, entire processes, and individual fabrication steps.

3.2.1 Equipment

```
510 class Equipment(Instrument, EntryData, ArchiveSection):
511
512     m_def = Section(
513         a_eeln={
514             'hide': [
515                 'lab_id',
516                 'datetime',
517             ],
518             'properties': {
519                 'order': [
520                     'name',
521                     'inventory_code',
522                     'affiliation',
523                     'product_model',
524                     'institution',
525                     'manufacturer_name',
526                     'is_bookable',
527                     'automatic_loading',
528                     'description',
529                 ],
530             },
```

```
531     }
532   )
533   inventory_code = Quantity(
534     type=int,
535     a_eIn={'component': 'NumberEditQuantity'},
536   )
537   affiliation = Quantity(
538     type=MEnum(
539       'NFFA-DI',
540       'iENTRANCE@ENL',
541     ),
542     a_eIn={'component': 'EnumEditQuantity'},
543   )
544   institution = Quantity(
545     type=str,
546     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
547   )
548   manufacturer_name = Quantity(
549     type=str,
550     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
551   )
552   product_model = Quantity(
553     type=str,
554     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
555   )
556   automatic_loading = Quantity(
557     type=bool,
558     a_eIn={'component': 'BoolEditQuantity'},
559   )
560   is_bookable = Quantity(
561     type=bool,
562     a_eIn={'component': 'BoolEditQuantity'},
563   )
564   capabilities = SubSection(
565     section_def=EquipmentParameterData,
566     repeats=True,
567   )
568   equipmentTechniques = SubSection(
569     section_def=EquipmentTechnique,
570     repeats=True,
571   )
572   permittedItems = SubSection(
573     section_def=EquipmentHasPermittedItemPropertyData,
574     repeats=True,
575   )
576   equipmentLogBook = SubSection(
577     section_def=Jobdone,
578     repeats=True,
579   )
580
581
582 class EquipmentReference(Link, ArchiveSection):
583   m_def = Section()
584
585   id = Quantity(
586     type=str,
587     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
588   )
589   notes = Quantity(
590     type=str,
591     a_eIn={'component': 'RichTextEditQuantity'},
592   )
593
```

```
594     section = Quantity(  
595         type=Instrument,  
596         a_eIn={'component': 'ReferenceEditQuantity'},  
597     )
```

Equipments are described using a set of quantities aimed at improving their findability within NOMAD. Among these, the boolean quantity "is_bookable" allows users to immediately identify whether a specific instrument is currently available for use in a fabrication process. The class includes several subsections, among which the most relevant is capabilities, which defines the machine's operational parameters and working ranges. As with the permittedItems section, we adopted a structure that includes a minimum value, maximum value, and a unit as a plain string, rather than associating each value with a separate Quantity. This design choice is due to certain limitations in NOMAD's current handling of dynamic quantity creation. For instance, the framework does not currently support user-defined quantities that are initially empty and modifiable directly through the interface. Altering this behavior would require modifying the NOMAD base package, which falls outside the scope of this work.

The *equipmentTechniques* subsection contains a catalog of the techniques available for each instrument, based on the taxonomy already cited. This ensures consistency between process steps and the instrumentation capabilities. Another important section is the *equipmentLogBook*, which functions as a registry of all tasks performed by the machine. A potential future improvement is to extend the *JobDone* class so that it includes the complete log file of each operation.

Lastly, we define the *EquipmentReference* class, used in subsequent sections to link a fabrication step to the instrument used. This class is built upon the *Link* base section, which allows pointing to a specific section within an *EntryArchive*. A *Link* contains two components: the name of the referenced section, and a *ReferenceEditQuantity*. In NOMAD, this type of quantity serves as a pointer to another archive entry, and includes the path to the JSON file representing that entry. This referencing system is particularly useful, as all instruments were uploaded to NOMAD through dedicated entries, and are then linked to the fabrication steps using the *EquipmentReference* class.

3.2.2 Fabrication processes

```
637 class FabricationProcess(EntryData, ArchiveSection):  
638
```

```
639 m_def = Section(  
640     a_eln={  
641         'properties': {  
642             'order': [  
643                 'name',  
644                 'project',  
645                 'affiliation',  
646                 'id_proposal',  
647                 'id_item_processed',  
648                 'locations',  
649                 'cost_model',  
650                 'description',  
651                 'author',  
652                 'starting_date',  
653                 'ending_date',  
654                 'generic_product_name',  
655                 'fabricationProductType',  
656                 'notes',  
657             ]  
658         },  
659         'hide': [  
660             'end_time',  
661             'datetime',  
662             'lab_id',  
663             'method',  
664             'location',  
665         ],  
666     },  
667 )  
668 id_proposal = Quantity(  
669     type=str,  
670     a_eln={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},  
671 )  
672 project = Quantity(  
673     type=str,  
674     a_eln={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},  
675 )  
676 id_item_processed = Quantity(  
677     type=str,  
678     a_eln={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},  
679 )  
680 affiliation = Quantity(  
681     type=MEnum(  
682         [  
683             'NFFA-DI',  
684             'iENTRANCE@ENL',  
685         ],  
686     ),  
687     a_eln={'component': 'EnumEditQuantity'},  
688 )  
689 locations = Quantity(  
690     type=str,  
691     shape=['*'],  
692     a_eln={  
693         'component': 'StringEditQuantity',  
694         'label': 'institutions',  
695     },  
696 )  
697 name = Quantity(  
698     type=str,  
699     a_eln={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},  
700 )  
701 description = Quantity(  

```

```
702     type=str,
703     a_eIn={'component': 'RichTextEditQuantity'},
704 )
705 author = Quantity(
706     type=str,
707     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
708 )
709 cost_model = Quantity(
710     type=str,
711     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
712 )
713 starting_date = Quantity(
714     type=Datetime,
715     a_eIn={'component': 'DateTimeEditQuantity'},
716 )
717 ending_date = Quantity(
718     type=Datetime,
719     a_eIn={'component': 'DateTimeEditQuantity'},
720 )
721 notes = Quantity(
722     type=str,
723     a_eIn={'component': 'RichTextEditQuantity'},
724 )
725 generic_product_name = Quantity(
726     type=str,
727     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
728 )
729 fabricationProductType = Quantity(
730     type=ListofProductType,
731     a_eIn={'component': 'ReferenceEditQuantity'},
732 )
733 steps = Quantity(
734     type=FabricationProcessStep,
735     shape=['*'],
736     a_eIn={'component': 'ReferenceEditQuantity'},
737 )
738 instruments = SubSection(
739     section_def=EquipmentReference,
740     repeats=True,
741 )
```

In the description of an entire fabrication process, we initially adopted a different approach from the actual, that is worth discussing to better understand the rationale behind the final solution.

As described in Sec.2.1, NOMAD provides a base class called `Process`, which can be used to represent any process composed of multiple steps. Our first attempt involved building the `FabricationProcess` class upon this base class, treating individual fabrication steps as subsections. This approach proved to be powerful, allowing the steps to be organized in sequence using ordered lists to preserve the actual process flow.

However, this structure turned out to be problematic in terms of findability. As discussed in Sec.2.1.2, NOMAD does not currently support searching for quantities whose paths are not explicitly defined. In the context of fabri-

cation processes, where many steps may be involved and their order is not necessarily fixed or strictly linear, this design quickly became impractical.

As a result, we decided instead to adopt a structure where each step is uploaded individually and then linked within the steps field of the FabricationProcess as a list of references. This means that when uploading a process, users must carefully maintain the desired step order manually by controlling the sequence in which references are added. While this requires some attention, it significantly improves the traceability and searchability of the process steps within NOMAD.

In addition to the list of steps, the FabricationProcess class contains a subsection for the instruments employed, as well as a fabricationProductType field, which can be selected from a minimal catalog provided in the plugin. The process also includes a rich set of geographical and chronological metadata, including a list of locations involved in the fabrication. This is particularly relevant in the context of the NFFA-DI initiative, where a single fabrication process might span multiple research facilities.

Importantly, the structure assumes an item-centric model, in which each process is ideally linked to a single item. While a real-world fabrication step may involve multiple items simultaneously, this atomistic representation provides a clear and traceable narrative for each item's fabrication history. This choice aligns with the primary objective of fabrication: transforming precursors into a final product, step by step.

3.2.3 Fabrication process steps

At this point, we can introduce the classes involved in the definition of fabrication steps.

```
369 class FabricationProcessStepBase(ProcessStep, ArchiveSection):
370
371     m_def = Section(
372         a_e1n={
373             'hide': [
374                 'comment',
375                 'duration',
376                 'start_time',
377             ],
378             'properties': {
379                 'order': [
380                     'job_number',
381                     'name',
382                     'description',
383                     'affiliation',
```

```

384         'location',
385         'operator',
386         'room',
387         'id_item_processed',
388         'starting_date',
389         'ending_date',
390         'step_type',
391         'definition_of_process_step',
392         'recipe_name',
393         'recipe_file',
394         'notes',
395     ],
396 },
397 },
398 )
399 job_number = Quantity(
400     type=int,
401     a_eIn={'component': 'NumberEditQuantity'},
402 )
403 name = Quantity(
404     type=str,
405     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
406 )
407 description = Quantity(
408     type=str,
409     a_eIn={'component': 'RichTextEditQuantity'},
410 )
411 affiliation = Quantity(
412     type=MEnum('NFFA-DI', 'iENTRANCE@ENL'),
413     a_eIn={'component': 'EnumEditQuantity'},
414 )
415 operator = Quantity(
416     type=str,
417     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
418 )
419 location = Quantity(
420     type=str,
421     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
422 )
423 room = Quantity(
424     type=str,
425     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
426 )
427 starting_date = Quantity(
428     type=Datetime,
429     a_eIn={'component': 'DateTimeEditQuantity'},
430 )
431 ending_date = Quantity(
432     type=Datetime,
433     a_eIn={'component': 'DateTimeEditQuantity'},
434 )
435 step_type = Quantity(
436     type=str,
437     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
438 )
439 id_item_processed = Quantity(
440     type=str,
441     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
442 )
443 definition_of_process_step = Quantity(
444     type=EquipmentTechnique,
445     a_eIn={'component': 'ReferenceEditQuantity'},
446 )

```

```

447     recipe_name = Quantity(
448         type=str,
449         a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
450     )
451     recipe_file = Quantity(
452         type=str,
453         a_eIn={'component': 'FileEditQuantity'},
454     )
455     notes = Quantity(
456         type=str,
457         a_eIn={'component': 'RichTextEditQuantity'},
458     )

```

The FabricationProcessStepBase class serves as the foundation for defining a fabrication step, which is then fully implemented in the FabricationProcessStep class. This distinction is essential due to the way Python handles class inheritance and modularization. Specifically, the base class does not include the instrument used for the step, which makes it reusable in different contexts. This is particularly useful when describing entries such as the JobDone class within an Equipment entry, where the instrument is already known and explicitly defined by the context.

```

600 class FabricationProcessStep(FabricationProcessStepBase, EntryData):
601
602     m_def = Section(
603         a_eIn={
604             'hide': [
605                 'comment',
606                 'duration',
607                 'start_time',
608             ],
609             'properties': {
610                 'order': [
611                     'job_number',
612                     'name',
613                     'description',
614                     'affiliation',
615                     'location',
616                     'operator',
617                     'room',
618                     'id_item_processed',
619                     'starting_date',
620                     'ending_date',
621                     'step_type',
622                     'definition_of_process_step',
623                     'recipe_name',
624                     'recipe_file',
625                     'notes',
626                 ],
627             },
628         },
629     )
630
631     instruments = SubSection(
632         section_def=EquipmentReference,
633         repeats=True,
634     )

```

The `FabricationProcessStep` class acts as a base class for all specific fabrication step types defined in separate files (see Appendix A). It includes a set of general-purpose fields that are common to all steps. These include: general information about the location, the ID of the item processed, chronological information and the recipe used for the step.

3.3 Apps

We already presented in Chapter 2 how to define a research app in NOMAD. All the necessary information has been provided in Section 2.1.2. In this section, we will instead focus on the visual structure and architecture of the implemented apps, providing examples and insights into the design decisions.

The required entry points are defined in the `"init.py"` file. Each entry point links to a corresponding app module, as in the following structure:

```
1 process_app_entry_point = AppEntryPoint(  
2     name='Fabrication_process_search',  
3     description='New app for equipment of fabrication facilities.',  
4     app=processapp,  
5 )
```

Each entry point points toward the app defined in the file `"equipmentapp.py"` for the equipment, to `"processapp.py"` for the whole processes and `"stepapp.py"` for the individual steps.

For the fabrication steps, we created a menu for each step type and collected them inside the `"menu_steps.py"` file, which is imported at the beginning of `"stepapp.py"`. Additionally, we created a centralized catalog of all available step types in the `"directories.py"` file. This helps improve readability and code linting, and acts as a reference point for all available fabrication step modules in the plugin.

3.3.1 Equipment

The app for managing equipment entries allows users (see Fig. 3.1) to filter and identify instruments based on key metadata such as location, NFFA-DI affiliation, and availability. In particular, instruments can be filtered by the techniques they support. This enables a typical user interested in performing a specific step to search for all compatible and bookable equipment across entries. The most important filters are clearly visible in the app's table columns, which display affiliation, availability (`"is_bookable"`), and the hosting laboratory.

```
1 from nomad.config.models.ui import (
2     App,
3     Column,
4     Menu,
5     MenuItemCustomQuantities,
6     MenuItemTerms,
7     SearchQuantities,
8 )
9
10 dir0 = 'fabrication_facilities.schema_packages.fabrication_utilities.Equipment'
11 Mainstr = 'data.equipmentTechniques.techniqueMainCategory'
12 Substr = 'data.equipmentTechniques.techniqueSubCategory'
13 gen = 'data.equipmentTechniques.genericEquipmentName'
14
15 equipmentapp = App(
16     label='Equipments&Techniques',
17     path='equipmentapp',
18     category='Fabrication facilities',
19     description='App to search fabrication equipments and useful techniques',
20     readme="""
21 This app allows to navigate through the equipments and techniques available in a
22 clean room system. You can search the techniques available and than the availability
23 of each instrument that has the desired technique included. At the end also the
24 instrument's location is findable.
25 """,
26     search_quantities=SearchQuantities(
27         include=[f'*#{dir0}'],
28     ),
29     columns=[
30         Column(quantity='entry_name', selected=True),
31         Column(quantity='entry_type'),
32         Column(
33             quantity=f'data.affiliation#{dir0}',
34             selected=True,
35         ),
36         Column(
37             quantity=f'data.institution#{dir0}',
38             selected=True,
39         ),
40         Column(
41             quantity=f'data.is_bookable#{dir0}',
42             selected=True,
43         ),
44         Column(quantity='upload_create_time', selected=True),
45     ],
46     filters_locked={'section_defs.definition_qualified_name': dir0},
47     menu=Menu(
48         items=[
49             MenuItemTerms(
50                 title='Affiliation',
51                 type='terms',
52                 search_quantity=f'data.affiliation#{dir0}',
53             ),
54             MenuItemTerms(
55                 title='Institution',
56                 type='terms',
57                 search_quantity=f'data.institution#{dir0}',
58             ),
59             MenuItemTerms(
60                 title='Availability',
61                 type='terms',
62                 search_quantity=f'data.is_bookable#{dir0}',
```


Figure 3.1: Visualization of the app for equipments entries.

```

63     ),
64     Menu(
65         title='Techniques',
66         indentation=0,
67         items=[
68             MenuItemTerms(
69                 title='Equipment class',
70                 type='terms',
71                 search_quantity=f'{gen}#{dir0}',
72             ),
73             MenuItemTerms(
74                 title='MainTechnique',
75                 type='terms',
76                 search_quantity=f'{Mainstr}#{dir0}',
77             ),
78             MenuItemTerms(
79                 title='fabrication step',
80                 type='terms',
81                 search_quantity=f'{Substr}#{dir0}',
82             ),
83         ],
84     ),
85     Menu(
86         title='User defined quantities',
87         items=[
88             MenuItemCustomQuantities(
89                 title='Costumer user quantities',
90                 type='custom_quantities',
91             ),
92         ],
93     ),
94 ],
95 ),
96 )

```

Initially, we attempted to include filters for equipment capabilities. However, due to the fact that capabilities are described as subsections (as discussed

in Sec. 3.2.1), they could not be effectively used as searchable filters in NOMAD. This led to the decision to exclude them from the current version of the app.

3.3.2 Fabrication processes

Some choices for the app for fabrication processes was designed according to the specific requirements of the NFFA-DI infrastructure. Key filters include: affiliation of the facility where the process was carried out, the proposal ID assigned to the fabrication request, "item processed" (i.e. the identifiers of the samples involved across different steps) and product type, to help categorize and identify the final outcome of the process. Columns in the app's table display all relevant metadata in a compact and user-friendly way.

```
1 from nomad.config.models.ui import (
2     App,
3     Column,
4     Menu,
5     MenuItemCustomQuantities,
6     MenuItemTerms,
7     SearchQuantities,
8 )
9
10 dir0 = 'fabrication_facilities.schema_packages.fabrication_utilities.FabricationProcess'
11 processapp = App(
12     label='Processes',
13     path='processesapp',
14     category='Fabrication facilities',
15     description='App to search fabrication processes.',
16     readme="""
17 This research app allows to search general information about fabrication processes.
18 You can search products, affiliation of the project and the item processed
19 """,
20     search_quantities=SearchQuantities(include=[f'*#{dir0}']),
21     columns=[
22         Column(quantity='entry_name', selected=True),
23         Column(quantity='entry_type'),
24         Column(
25             quantity=f'data.affiliation#{dir0}',
26             selected=True,
27         ),
28         Column(
29             quantity=f'data.id_proposal#{dir0}',
30             selected=True,
31         ),
32         Column(
33             quantity=f'data.generic_product_name#{dir0}',
34             selected=True,
35         ),
36         Column(
37             quantity=f'data.id_item_processed#{dir0}',
38             selected=True,
39         ),
40         Column(quantity='upload_create_time', selected=True),
41     ],
42     filters_locked={'section_defs.definition_qualified_name': dir0},
```

```
43     menu=Menu(  
44         items=[  
45             MenuItemTerms(  
46                 title='Affiliation',  
47                 type='terms',  
48                 search_quantity=f'data.affiliation#{dir0}',  
49             ),  
50             MenuItemTerms(  
51                 title='ID proposal',  
52                 type='terms',  
53                 search_quantity=f'data.id_proposal#{dir0}',  
54             ),  
55             MenuItemTerms(  
56                 title='Product Type',  
57                 type='terms',  
58                 search_quantity=f'data.generic_product_name#{dir0}',  
59             ),  
60             MenuItemTerms(  
61                 title='ID item processed',  
62                 type='terms',  
63                 search_quantity=f'data.id_item_processed#{dir0}',  
64             ),  
65             MenuItemTerms(  
66                 title='Author',  
67                 type='terms',  
68                 search_quantity=f'data.author#{dir0}',  
69             ),  
70             Menu(  
71                 title='User defined quantities',  
72                 items=[  
73                     MenuItemCustomQuantities(  
74                         title='Costumer user quantities',  
75                         type='custom_quantities',  
76                     ),  
77                 ],  
78             ),  
79         ],  
80     ),  
81 )
```

3.3.3 Fabrication process steps

The app for the fabrication steps includes a large number of menus, each corresponding to a specific step type. Due to the extensive number of these menus, they are not presented in detail within this thesis. However, their full implementation can be accessed at the GitHub repository: [Fabrication-utilities](#). Here, we present the general structure of the app for the steps:

```
1 from nomad.config.models.ui import (  
2     App,  
3     Column,  
4     Menu,  
5     MenuItemCustomQuantities,  
6     SearchQuantities,  
7 )  
8
```


Figure 3.2: Visualization of the app for the global processes entries

```

9 from fabrication_facilities.apps.directories import dir_path
10 from fabrication_facilities.apps.menu_steps import (
11     menuadd_bonding,
12     menuadd_electrongun,
13     menuadd_icpcvd,
14     menuadd_sog,
15     menuadd_spincoat,
16     menuadd_sputtering,
17     menuremove_drie,
18     menuremove_rie,
19     menuremove_stripping,
20     menuremove_wetclean,
21     menuremove_wetetching,
22     menutrans_baking,
23     menutrans_annealing,
24     menutrans_develop,
25     menutrans_dicing,
26     menutrans_doping,
27     menutrans_ebl,
28     menutrans_fib,
29     menutrans_labelingcleaning,
30     menutrans_ltodensification,
31     menutrans_sod,
32     menutrans_thermaloxidation,
33     menutrans_track,
34     menuutils_obsmeasurements,
35     menuutils_startingmaterial,
36 )
37
38 schemas = [f'#{path_value}' for path_value in dir_path.values()]
39 fps = 'FabricationProcessStep'
40 dir0 = f'fabrication_facilities.schema_packages.fabrication_utilities.{fps}'
41 schemas.append(f'#{dir0}')
42
43 stepapp = App(
44     label='Fabrication steps',
45     path='stepapp',
46     category='Fabrication facilities',
47     description='App to search fabrication processes.',

```

```

48     readme="""
49     This app is intended to navigate around the ecosystem of clean room fabrication
50     possible steps. At the beginning you can see all the fabrication steps available
51     in nomad and than through the filters you can specialize the research per single
52     technique. Navigation that consists in multiple technique is not allowed.
53     """
54     search_quantities=SearchQuantities(include=schemas),
55     columns=[
56         Column(quantity='entry_name', selected=True),
57         Column(quantity='entry_type', selected=True),
58         Column(
59             quantity=f'data.affiliation#{dir0}',
60             selected=True,
61         ),
62         Column(
63             quantity=f'data.location#{dir0}',
64             selected=True,
65         ),
66         Column(quantity='upload_create_time', selected=True),
67     ],
68     filters_locked={'section_defs.definition_qualified_name': dir0},
69     menu=Menu(
70         items=[
71             Menu(
72                 title='Add steps',
73                 indentation=0,
74                 items=[
75                     Menu(
76                         title='Bonding',
77                         items=[
78                             menuadd_bonding,
79                         ],
80                     ),
81                     Menu(
82                         title='Integration',
83                         items=[],
84                     ),
85                     Menu(
86                         title='Synthesis',
87                         items=[
88                             menuadd_icpcvd,
89                             menuadd_spincoat,
90                             menuadd_electrongun,
91                             menuadd_sputtering,
92                             menuadd_sog,
93                         ],
94                     ),
95                 ],
96             ),
97             Menu(
98                 title='Transform steps',
99                 indentation=0,
100                items=[
101                    Menu(
102                        title='Dicing',
103                        items=[
104                            menutrans_dicing,
105                        ],
106                    ),
107                    Menu(
108                        title='Doping',
109                        items=[
110                            menutrans_doping,

```

```

111         menutrans_sod,
112     ],
113 ),
114 Menu(
115     title='Lithography',
116     items=[
117         menutrans_ebl,
118         menutrans_fib,
119         menutrans_track,
120     ],
121 ),
122 Menu(
123     title='Solution modification',
124     items=[
125         menutrans_develop,
126     ],
127 ),
128 Menu(
129     title='Thermal processing',
130     items=[
131         menutrans_annealing,
132         menutrans_ltodensification,
133         menutrans_thermaloxidation,
134         menutrans_baking,
135     ],
136 ),
137 Menu(
138     title='Labeling',
139     items=[
140         menutrans_labelingcleaning,
141     ],
142 ),
143 ],
144 ),
145 Menu(
146     title='Remove steps',
147     indentation=0,
148     items=[
149         Menu(
150             title='Etching',
151             items=[
152                 menuremove_drie,
153                 menuremove_wetclean,
154                 menuremove_rie,
155                 menuremove_wetetching,
156                 menuremove_stripping,
157             ],
158         ),
159     ],
160 ),
161 Menu(
162     title='Starting material',
163     items=[
164         menuutils_startingmaterial,
165     ],
166 ),
167 Menu(
168     title='Measurements',
169     items=[
170         menuutils_obsmeasurements,
171     ],
172 ),
173 Menu(

```

```
174         title='User defined quantities',
175         items=[
176             MenuItemCustomQuantities(
177                 title='Costumer user quantities',
178                 type='custom_quantities',
179             ),
180         ],
181     ),
182 ],
183 ),
184 )
```

Within the app's table, one of the key visible quantities is the "entry_type". This attribute is automatically assigned by NOMAD when an upload is created and corresponds to the name of the schema used to represent the data. This design allows users to immediately identify the specific type of fabrication step, as each schema is named after the class following the taxonomy discussed earlier.

We chose to implement a nested menu structure for this app, which mirrors the taxonomy defined for fabrication steps. This hierarchical approach enables intuitive navigation: for example, if a user wishes to search for deposition steps employing the ICP-CVD technique, they can follow the path "add/synthesis/ICP_CVD" to reach the corresponding menu and apply any available filters specifically built for that schema.

Chapter 4

Results and conclusions

In this chapter, we present the output and visualization of the Nomad platform plugin, following the process described in Section 1.3. Starting from the choice of which distribution to employ for the Trento servers, we move on to describe the results of the entire pipeline. The JSON files uploaded to Nomad are provided in Appendix B. Finally, some concluding remarks are presented.

4.1 Uploads in nomad

At the end of this phase, we set up a development distribution on the local server of CNR in Trento. This choice, preferred over the installation of the full Oasis services, was based on a careful evaluation of the pros and cons. A non-Oasis installation certainly lacks some of the powerful features available in a full NOMAD environment, such as external NORTH utilities that allow running Jupyter Notebooks and other useful tools directly within Nomad.

Nevertheless, due to the limited time available, the installation of a development distribution proved crucial. It eliminated the need to create ad hoc Docker images and allowed for a faster implementation. Moreover, the deployment method of a plugin differs between the two systems. In the development distribution (the only one studied and implemented), plugins are installed as submodules within a dedicated application folder. As a result, a simple "git pull" command is sufficient to update the system. This was highly beneficial for our work, as numerous corrections and extensive debugging are typically required during plugin development. Consequently, a significant amount of time was saved thanks to this approach.

Importantly, this choice did not compromise the general results and performance of the plugin, which integrated very well into the ideal pipeline presented in Chapter 1. As previously mentioned, the JSON files uploaded to Nomad are listed in Appendix B. Here, we only provide some general information about the steps followed during the process.

First, we expanded the Fablims database to include some recipes that are fully FAIR compliant. The recipes presented in Section 1.3 were written ad hoc to support a FAIR-compliant pipeline. While these recipes could certainly be further enriched to improve the data and metadata structure, they represent an important step toward the full FAIRification of the process. Moreover, we enabled in Fablims the possibility to send data directly to the NOMAD repository built on the server, thanks to an option that will become available in FABlims once more recipes and tests are provided. Regarding

Figure 4.1: Export option as visualized in fablims.

the representation of the process, it worked very well: all steps and the entire workflow were correctly indexed and are now searchable within [NOMAD Trento](#). For further details, you can navigate the Nomad Trento platform and test the functionality of the search interface. Entries are also visible to guest users who are not logged in.

4.2 Final remarks and conclusions

The plugin performed well within the scope of the simple pipeline proposed in this work, successfully supporting the upload and indexing of data in the NOMAD platform. However, as also highlighted throughout the text, there are several functionalities that still need to be improved and expanded. In particular, further development is required in the handling of the properties of items and instruments. Addressing these aspects would allow for a more detailed and flexible data structure, thereby enhancing the overall FAIRness of the pipeline.

A discussion with the FAIRmat team could be particularly valuable to explore possible solutions to the current limitations in data discoverability,

as well as to evaluate options for dynamically managing physical quantities within the platform. Such collaboration may help identify strategies to enhance the flexibility and scalability of the system. Therefore, while the work carried out represents a significant step forward, further developments are essential to extend the plugin’s capabilities and ensure its effective application in more complex and data-rich experimental scenarios.

After all, if FAIR is itself a form of science—and not merely a way to conduct it—then, just like science and progress, it is likely that its development will never truly come to an end.

Appendix A

Fabrication process steps

A.1 Add steps

A.1.1 ICP CVD

The ICP CVD process is defined within the following class:

```
40 class ICP_CVD(Chemical, FabricationProcessStep, ArchiveSection):
41     """
42     Class autogenerated from yaml schema.
43     """
44
45     m_def = Section(
46         a_eIn={
47             'hide': [
48                 'description',
49                 'lab_id',
50                 'datetime',
51                 'comment',
52                 'duration',
53                 'end_time',
54                 'start_time',
55             ],
56             'properties': {
57                 'order': [
58                     'job_number',
59                     'name',
60                     'description',
61                     'affiliation',
62                     'location',
63                     'operator',
64                     'room',
65                     'id_item_processed',
66                     'starting_date',
67                     'ending_date',
68                     'step_type',
69                     'definition_of_process_step',
70                     'recipe_name',
71                     'recipe_file',
72                     'short_name',
73                     'chemical_formula',
```

```

74         'duration_target',
75         'thickness_target',
76         'deposition_rate_target',
77         'chamber_pressure',
78         'chuck_temperature',
79         'chuck_power',
80         'chuck_frequency',
81         'icp_power',
82         'icp_frequency',
83         'bias',
84         'thickness_measured',
85         'duration_measured',
86         'deposition_rate_obtained',
87         'notes',
88     ]
89 },
90 ),
91 )
92 deposition_rate_target = Quantity(
93     type=np.float64,
94     description='Deposition rate desired',
95     a_eIn={
96         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
97         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm/minute',
98     },
99     unit='nm/minute',
100 )
101 short_name = Quantity(
102     type=str,
103     description='Material to be deposited',
104     a_eIn={
105         'component': 'StringEditQuantity',
106         'label': 'target material',
107     },
108 )
109 chemical_formula = Quantity(
110     type=str,
111     description='Formula of the material target. Insert only if known',
112     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
113 )
114 thickness_target = Quantity(
115     type=np.float64,
116     description='Amount of material to be deposited',
117     a_eIn={
118         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
119         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm',
120     },
121     unit='nm',
122 )
123 chamber_pressure = Quantity(
124     type=np.float64,
125     description='Pressure in the chamber',
126     a_eIn={
127         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
128         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'mbar',
129     },
130     unit='mbar',
131 )
132 chuck_temperature = Quantity(
133     type=np.float64,
134     description='Temperature of the chuck',
135     a_eIn={
136         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',

```

```
137         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'celsius',
138     },
139     unit='celsius',
140 )
141 chuck_power = Quantity(
142     type=np.float64,
143     description='Power erogated on the chuck',
144     a_eIn={
145         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
146         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'watt',
147     },
148     unit='watt',
149 )
150 chuck_frequency = Quantity(
151     type=np.float64,
152     description='Frequency of current on the chuck',
153     a_eIn={
154         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
155         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'MHz',
156     },
157     unit='MHz',
158 )
159 icp_power = Quantity(
160     type=np.float64,
161     description='Power erogated in the region of the plasma',
162     a_eIn={
163         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
164         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'watt',
165     },
166     unit='watt',
167 )
168 icp_frequency = Quantity(
169     type=np.float64,
170     description='Frequency of current on the gases area',
171     a_eIn={
172         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
173         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'MHz',
174     },
175     unit='MHz',
176 )
177 bias = Quantity(
178     type=np.float64,
179     description='Bias voltage in the chamber',
180     a_eIn={
181         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
182         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'volt',
183     },
184     unit='volt',
185 )
186 thickness_measured = Quantity(
187     type=np.float64,
188     description='Actual amount of material deposited in the process',
189     a_eIn={
190         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
191         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm',
192     },
193     unit='nm',
194 )
195 duration_target = Quantity(
196     type=np.float64,
197     description='Duration required of the process',
198     a_eIn={
199         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
```

```

200         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'minute',
201     },
202     unit='minute',
203 )
204 duration_measured = Quantity(
205     type=np.float64,
206     description='Real time employed',
207     a_eIn={
208         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
209         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'minute',
210     },
211     unit='minute',
212 )
213 deposition_rate_obtained = Quantity(
214     type=np.float64,
215     description='Deposition rate as output',
216     a_eIn={
217         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
218         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm/minute',
219     },
220     unit='nm/minute',
221 )
222 fluximeters = SubSection(
223     section_def=Massflow_controller,
224     repeats=True,
225 )
226 material_elemental_composition = SubSection(
227     section_def=ElementalComposition, repeats=True
228 )
229
230 def normalize(self, archive: 'EntryArchive', logger: 'BoundLogger') -> None:
231     super().normalize(archive, logger)
232     if self.chemical_formula:
233         elements, counts = parse_chemical_formula(self.chemical_formula)
234         total = 0
235         for token in counts:
236             total += int(token)
237         mass = sum(am[an[el]] * cou for el, cou in zip(elements, counts))
238         if total != 0:
239             elemental_fraction = np.array(counts) / total
240             elementality = []
241             i = 0
242             for entry in elements:
243                 elemental_try = ElementalComposition()
244                 elemental_try.element = entry
245                 elemental_try.atomic_fraction = elemental_fraction[i]
246                 mass_frac = (am[an[entry]] * counts[i]) / mass
247                 elemental_try.mass_fraction = mass_frac
248                 i += 1
249             elementality.append(elemental_try)
250         else:
251             print('No elements provided')
252     self.material_elemental_composition = elementality

```

A comprehensive set of data parameters is employed to describe the deposition technique, ensuring a detailed characterization of the process. Furthermore, a clear distinction is made between target and measured quantities. This distinction is essential, as fabrication processes inherently involve ideal process parameters that may not be perfectly achieved due to uncontrollable variables. Consequently, measured values serve as control variables, allowing

for real-time process monitoring.

This class consists of two subsections: fluximeters which utilizes the `Massflow_Controller` class presented in 3 to describe the gas flow dynamics within the chamber and the "material_elemental_composition" contains "ElementalComposition" classes used to characterize the chemical composition of the deposited material. This subsection is normalized using the `normalize` function, similar to its application in the `Massflow_Controller` class..

A.1.2 Spin coating

```
255 class Spin_Coating(Chemical, FabricationProcessStep, ArchiveSection):
256     m_def = Section(
257         a_eIn={
258             'hide': [
259                 'description',
260                 'lab_id',
261                 'datetime',
262                 'comment',
263                 'duration',
264                 'end_time',
265                 'start_time',
266             ],
267             'properties': {
268                 'order': [
269                     'job_number',
270                     'name',
271                     'description',
272                     'affiliation',
273                     'location',
274                     'operator',
275                     'room',
276                     'id_item_processed',
277                     'starting_date',
278                     'ending_date',
279                     'step_type',
280                     'definition_of_process_step',
281                     'recipe_name',
282                     'recipe_file',
283                     'short_name',
284                     'chemical_formula',
285                     'thickness_target',
286                     'hdms_required',
287                     'exposure_required',
288                     'exposure_intensity',
289                     'exposure_duration',
290                     'peb_required',
291                     'peb_duration',
292                     'peb_temperature',
293                     'dewetting_duration',
294                     'dewetting_temperature',
295                     'spin_dispensed_volume',
296                     'spin_frequency',
297                     'spin_angular_acceleration',
298                     'spin_duration',
299                     'baking_required',
300                     'baking_duration',
```

```

301         'baking_temperature',
302         'thickness_measured',
303         'notes',
304     ]
305     },
306 },
307 )
308 short_name = Quantity(
309     type=str,
310     description='Type of resist to be deposited',
311     a_eIn={
312         'component': 'StringEditQuantity',
313         'label': 'resist name',
314     },
315 )
316 chemical_formula = Quantity(
317     type=str,
318     description='Resist formula. Insert only if known',
319     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
320 )
321 thickness_target = Quantity(
322     type=np.float64,
323     description='Amount of resist to be deposited',
324     a_eIn={
325         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
326         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm',
327     },
328     unit='nm',
329 )
330 hdms_required = Quantity(
331     type=bool,
332     description='The recipe use the hdms?',
333     a_eIn={'component': 'BoolEditQuantity'},
334 )
335 exposure_required = Quantity(
336     type=bool,
337     description='The recipe use exposure?',
338     a_eIn={'component': 'BoolEditQuantity'},
339 )
340 exposure_intensity = Quantity(
341     type=np.float64,
342     description='Power per area in the exposure',
343     a_eIn={
344         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
345         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'mwatt/cm^2',
346     },
347     unit='mwatt/cm^2',
348 )
349 exposure_duration = Quantity(
350     type=np.float64,
351     description='The duration of the exposure',
352     a_eIn={
353         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
354         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'sec',
355     },
356     unit='sec',
357 )
358 peb_required = Quantity(
359     type=bool,
360     description='The recipe needs PEB?',
361     a_eIn={'component': 'BoolEditQuantity'},
362 )
363 peb_duration = Quantity(

```

```
364     type=np.float64,
365     description='The duration of the peb',
366     a_eIn={
367         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
368         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'sec',
369     },
370     unit='sec',
371 )
372 peb_temperature = Quantity(
373     type=np.float64,
374     description='The temperature of the peb',
375     a_eIn={
376         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
377         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'celsius',
378     },
379     unit='celsius',
380 )
381 dewetting_duration = Quantity(
382     type=np.float64,
383     description='The duration of the dewetting',
384     a_eIn={
385         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
386         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'minute',
387     },
388     unit='minute',
389 )
390 dewetting_temperature = Quantity(
391     type=np.float64,
392     description='The temperaure of the dewetting',
393     a_eIn={
394         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
395         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'celsius',
396     },
397     unit='celsius',
398 )
399 spin_dispensed_volume = Quantity(
400     type=np.float64,
401     description='Solution dispensed',
402     a_eIn={
403         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
404         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'milliliter',
405     },
406     unit='milliliter',
407 )
408 spin_frequency = Quantity(
409     type=np.float64,
410     description='Velocity of the spinner',
411     a_eIn={
412         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
413         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'revolutions_per_minute',
414     },
415     unit='revolutions_per_minute',
416 )
417 spin_angular_acceleration = Quantity(
418     type=np.float64,
419     description='Acceleration of the spinner',
420     a_eIn={
421         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
422         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'revolutions_per_minute/sec',
423     },
424     unit='revolutions_per_minute/sec',
425 )
426 spin_duration = Quantity(
```

```

427         type=np.float64,
428         description='Acceleration of the spinner',
429         a_eln={
430             'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
431             'defaultDisplayUnit': 'sec',
432         },
433         unit='sec',
434     )
435     baking_required = Quantity(
436         type=bool,
437         description='The recipe use baking?',
438         a_eln={
439             'component': 'BoolEditQuantity',
440         },
441     )
442     baking_duration = Quantity(
443         type=np.float64,
444         description='The duration of the baking',
445         a_eln={
446             'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
447             'defaultDisplayUnit': 'minute',
448         },
449         unit='minute',
450     )
451     baking_temperature = Quantity(
452         type=np.float64,
453         description='The temperaure of the baking',
454         a_eln={
455             'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
456             'defaultDisplayUnit': 'celsius',
457         },
458         unit='celsius',
459     )
460     thickness_measured = Quantity(
461         type=np.float64,
462         description='Actual amount of resist deposited',
463         a_eln={
464             'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
465             'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm',
466         },
467         unit='nm',
468     )
469
470     resist_elemental_composition = SubSection(
471         section_def=ElementalComposition, repeats=True
472     )
473
474     def normalize(self, archive: 'EntryArchive', logger: 'BoundLogger') -> None:
475         super().normalize(archive, logger)
476         if self.chemical_formula:
477             elements, counts = parse_chemical_formula(self.chemical_formula)
478             total = 0
479             for token in counts:
480                 total += int(token)
481             mass = sum(am[an[el]] * cou for el, cou in zip(elements, counts))
482             if total != 0:
483                 elemental_fraction = np.array(counts) / total
484                 elementality = []
485                 i = 0
486                 for entry in elements:
487                     elemental_try = ElementalComposition()
488                     elemental_try.element = entry
489                     elemental_try.atomic_fraction = elemental_fraction[i]

```

```
490         mass_frac = (am[an[entry]] * counts[i]) / mass
491         elemental_try.mass_fraction = mass_frac
492         i += 1
493         elementality.append(elemental_try)
494     else:
495         print('No elements provided')
496     self.resist_elemental_composition = elementality
```

The SpinCoating class describes the resist deposition process using a spinner. The selected parameters comprehensively represent the entire procedure required to achieve the final coated resist layer. The process may involve adhesion promoters such as HDMS, successive steps of exposure and post exposure baking with a final dewetting. Following these preliminary steps, the actual spinning process is defined, concluding with a final baking step to solidify the resist layer. The only output parameter considered in this model is the final thickness of the resist layer. Additionally, a subsection is dedicated to the elemental composition of the resist. Since resists are typically complex polymers or chemical compounds, their exact formulas may not always be known. However, this feature is included to allow for completeness.

A.2 Remove steps

A.2.1 ICP-RIE

```
44 class DRIE(Chemical, FabricationProcessStep, ArchiveSection):
45
46     m_def = Section(
47         a_eIn={
48             'hide': [
49                 'description',
50                 'lab_id',
51                 'datetime',
52                 'comment',
53                 'duration',
54                 'end_time',
55                 'start_time',
56             ],
57         'properties': {
58             'order': [
59                 'job_number',
60                 'name',
61                 'description',
62                 'affiliation',
63                 'location',
64                 'operator',
65                 'room',
66                 'id_item_processed',
67                 'starting_date',
68                 'ending_date',
69                 'step_type',
70                 'definition_of_process_step',
71                 'recipe_name',
```

```

72         'recipe_file',
73         'short_name',
74         'chemical_formula',
75         'depth_target',
76         'duration_target',
77         'etching_rate_target',
78         'chamber_pressure',
79         'chuck_temperature',
80         'chuck_power',
81         'chuck_frequency',
82         'icp_power',
83         'icp_frequency',
84         'bias',
85         'depth_measured',
86         'duration_measured',
87         'etching_rate_obtained',
88         'notes',
89     ]
90     },
91 },
92 )
93 etching_rate_target = Quantity(
94     type=np.float64,
95     description='etching rate desired',
96     a_eIn={
97         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
98         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm/minute',
99     },
100     unit='nm/minute',
101 )
102 duration_target = Quantity(
103     type=np.float64,
104     description='Time prescribed by the recipe',
105     a_eIn={
106         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
107         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'minute',
108     },
109     unit='minute',
110 )
111 short_name = Quantity(
112     type=str,
113     description='Material to be etched',
114     a_eIn={
115         'component': 'StringEditQuantity',
116         'label': 'target material',
117     },
118 )
119 chemical_formula = Quantity(
120     type=str,
121     description='Inserted only if known',
122     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
123 )
124 depth_target = Quantity(
125     type=np.float64,
126     description='Amount of material to be etched',
127     a_eIn={
128         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
129         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm',
130     },
131     unit='nm',
132 )
133 chamber_pressure = Quantity(
134     type=np.float64,

```

```

135     description='Pressure in the chamber',
136     a_eIn={
137         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
138         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'mbar',
139     },
140     unit='mbar',
141 )
142 chuck_temperature = Quantity(
143     type=np.float64,
144     description='Temperature of the chuck',
145     a_eIn={
146         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
147         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'celsius',
148     },
149     unit='celsius',
150 )
151 chuck_power = Quantity(
152     type=np.float64,
153     description='Power erogated on the chuck',
154     a_eIn={
155         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
156         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'watt',
157     },
158     unit='watt',
159 )
160 chuck_frequency = Quantity(
161     type=np.float64,
162     description='Frequency of current on the chuck',
163     a_eIn={
164         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
165         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'MHz',
166     },
167     unit='MHz',
168 )
169 icp_power = Quantity(
170     type=np.float64,
171     description='Power erogated in the region of the plasma',
172     a_eIn={
173         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
174         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'watt',
175     },
176     unit='watt',
177 )
178 icp_frequency = Quantity(
179     type=np.float64,
180     description='Frequency of current on the gases area',
181     a_eIn={
182         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
183         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'MHz',
184     },
185     unit='MHz',
186 )
187 bias = Quantity(
188     type=np.float64,
189     description='Bias voltage in the chamber',
190     a_eIn={
191         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
192         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'volt',
193     },
194     unit='volt',
195 )
196 depth_measured = Quantity(
197     type=np.float64,

```

```

198     description='Amount of material etched effectively in the process',
199     a_eIn={
200         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
201         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm',
202     },
203     unit='nm',
204 )
205 duration_measured = Quantity(
206     type=np.float64,
207     description='Real time of the process ad output',
208     a_eIn={
209         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
210         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'minute',
211     },
212     unit='minute',
213 )
214 etching_rate_obtained = Quantity(
215     type=np.float64,
216     description='Etching rate as output',
217     a_eIn={
218         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
219         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm/minute',
220     },
221     unit='nm/minute',
222 )
223 fluximeters = SubSection(
224     section_def=Massflow_controller,
225     repeats=True,
226 )
227 material_elemental_composition = SubSection(
228     section_def=ElementalComposition, repeats=True
229 )
230
231 def normalize(self, archive: 'EntryArchive', logger: 'BoundLogger') -> None:
232     super().normalize(archive, logger)
233     if self.chemical_formula:
234         elements, counts = parse_chemical_formula(self.chemical_formula)
235         total = 0
236         for token in counts:
237             total += int(token)
238         mass = sum(am[an[el]] * cou for el, cou in zip(elements, counts))
239         if total != 0:
240             elemental_fraction = np.array(counts) / total
241             elementality = []
242             i = 0
243             for entry in elements:
244                 elemental_try = ElementalComposition()
245                 elemental_try.element = entry
246                 elemental_try.atomic_fraction = elemental_fraction[i]
247                 mass_frac = (am[an[entry]] * counts[i]) / mass
248                 elemental_try.mass_fraction = mass_frac
249                 i += 1
250                 elementality.append(elemental_try)
251             else:
252                 print('No elements provided')
253             self.material_elemental_composition = elementality

```

The DRIE class represents dry etching processes, specifically ICP RIE (Inductively Coupled Plasma Reactive Ion Etching). Structurally, it is very similar to the ICP CVD class described earlier. The main differences are the

names of the quantities which are labeled by terms like depth and etching instead of thickness and deposition.

A.2.2 Wet cleaning

```

381 class WetCleaning(FabricationProcessStep, ArchiveSection):
382     m_def = Section(
383         a_eIn={
384             'hide': [
385                 'description',
386                 'lab_id',
387                 'datetime',
388                 'comment',
389                 'duration',
390                 'end_time',
391                 'start_time',
392             ],
393             'properties': {
394                 'order': [
395                     'job_number',
396                     'name',
397                     'description',
398                     'affiliation',
399                     'location',
400                     'operator',
401                     'room',
402                     'id_item_processed',
403                     'starting_date',
404                     'ending_date',
405                     'step_type',
406                     'definition_of_process_step',
407                     'recipe_name',
408                     'recipe_file',
409                     'removing_solution',
410                     'removing_solution_proportions',
411                     'removing_duration',
412                     'removing_temperature',
413                     'rising_solution',
414                     'rising_solution_proportions',
415                     'rising_duration',
416                     'notes',
417                 ]
418             },
419         ),
420     )
421     removing_solution = Quantity(
422         type=str,
423         description='Remover solution name' ,
424         a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
425     )
426     removing_solution_proportions = Quantity(
427         type=str,
428         description='Proportions used for the remover',
429         a_eIn={
430             'component': 'StringEditQuantity',
431         },
432     )
433     removing_duration = Quantity(
434         type=np.float64,
435         description='Removing duration',
  
```

```
436     a_eIn={
437         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
438         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'minute',
439     },
440     unit='minute',
441 )
442 removing_temperature = Quantity(
443     type=np.float64,
444     description='Temperature employed for the removing',
445     a_eIn={
446         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
447         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'celsius',
448     },
449     unit='celsius',
450 )
451 rising_solution = Quantity(
452     description='Cleaner solution',
453     type=str,
454     a_eIn={
455         'component': 'StringEditQuantity',
456     },
457 )
458 rising_solution_proportions = Quantity(
459     type=str,
460     description='Proportions used for the remover',
461     a_eIn={
462         'component': 'StringEditQuantity',
463     },
464 )
465 rising_duration = Quantity(
466     type=np.float64,
467     description='Cleaning duration',
468     a_eIn={
469         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
470         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'minute',
471     },
472     unit='minute',
473 )
```

The `WetCleaning` class describes processes in which residual material must be removed from a sample surface. It consists of a few key parameters: those used to describe the remover solution are identified by the prefix `"removing_"` and parameters used to describe the final cleaning identified by the prefix `"rising_"`. In our example test workflows wet etching is used to remove residual resist from the surface.

A.3 Transform steps

A.3.1 FIB/EBL

Both Electron Beam Lithography (EBL) and Focused Ion Beam (FIB) are conceptually similar processes, as discussed in Chapter 1. Due to their practical equivalence, a single class, `FIB`, here is presented. This class includes all EBL-related parameters, with one additional feature of the parameter

number of loops, that represents the number of iterations performed during the operation..

```

177 class FIB(FabricationProcessStep, ArchiveSection):
178
179     m_def = Section(
180         a_eIn={
181             'hide': [
182                 'description',
183                 'lab_id',
184                 'datetime',
185                 'comment',
186                 'duration',
187                 'end_time',
188                 'start_time',
189             ],
190             'properties': {
191                 'order': [
192                     'job_number',
193                     'name',
194                     'description',
195                     'affiliation',
196                     'location',
197                     'operator',
198                     'room',
199                     'id_item_processed',
200                     'starting_date',
201                     'ending_date',
202                     'step_type',
203                     'definition_of_process_step',
204                     'recipe_name',
205                     'recipe_file',
206                     'dose',
207                     'writing_field_dimension',
208                     'address_size',
209                     'clock',
210                     'chamber_pressure',
211                     'chuck_temperature',
212                     'tension',
213                     'current',
214                     'alignment_required',
215                     'alignment_max_error',
216                     'number_of_loops',
217                     'notes',
218                 ]
219             },
220         },
221     )
222     recipe_name = Quantity(
223         type=str,
224         description='Name of the file that contains the geometry to impress',
225         a_eIn={
226             'label': 'file CAD name',
227             'component': 'StringEditQuantity',
228         },
229     )
230     dose = Quantity(
231         type=np.float64,
232         description='Dose used in the process',
233         a_eIn={
234             'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
235             'defaultDisplayUnit': 'uC/centimeter^2',

```

```
236     },
237     unit='uC/centimeter^2',
238 )
239 writing_field_dimension = Quantity(
240     type=np.float64,
241     description='Area covered globally in the process',
242     a_eIn={
243         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
244         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'um^2',
245     },
246     unit='um^2',
247 )
248 address_size = Quantity(
249     type=np.float64,
250     description='The minimum distance covered per step in the process',
251     a_eIn={
252         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
253         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm',
254     },
255     unit='nm',
256 )
257 clock = Quantity(
258     type=np.float64,
259     description='Frequency used',
260     a_eIn={
261         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
262         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'MHz',
263     },
264     unit='MHz',
265 )
266 current = Quantity(
267     type=np.float64,
268     description='Current provided',
269     a_eIn={
270         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
271         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'pampere',
272     },
273     unit='pampere',
274 )
275 chamber_pressure = Quantity(
276     type=np.float64,
277     description='Pressure in the chamber',
278     a_eIn={
279         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
280         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'mbar',
281     },
282     unit='mbar',
283 )
284 chuck_temperature = Quantity(
285     type=np.float64,
286     description='Temperature of the chuck',
287     a_eIn={
288         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
289         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'celsius',
290     },
291     unit='celsius',
292 )
293 tension = Quantity(
294     type=np.float64,
295     description='Voltage accelerating the ions',
296     a_eIn={
297         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
298         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'volt',
```

```

299     },
300     unit='volt',
301   )
302   alignment_required = Quantity(
303     type=bool,
304     description='Alignment is required in the patterning?',
305     a_eIn={'component': 'BoolEditQuantity'},
306   )
307   alignment_max_error = Quantity(
308     type=np.float64,
309     description='Maximum error allowed in the alignment',
310     a_eIn={
311       'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
312       'defaultDisplayUnit': 'nm',
313     },
314     unit='nm',
315   )
316   number_of_loops = Quantity(
317     type=int,
318     description='Iteration of the process',
319     a_eIn={'component': 'NumberEditQuantity'},
320   )

```

In this case, the recipe file is replaced by a CAD file, which serves as the primary input for instrument configuration. Other key parameters are those used to describe the SEM-like beam and the variables labelled by "alignment_" used to give minimal information about the alignment. For precise alignment details, the CAD file can be referenced if uploaded.

A.3.2 Resist development

```

323 class ResistDevelopment(FabricationProcessStep, ArchiveSection):
324
325     m_def = Section(
326         a_eIn={
327             'hide': [
328                 'description',
329                 'lab_id',
330                 'datetime',
331                 'comment',
332                 'duration',
333                 'end_time',
334                 'start_time',
335             ],
336             'properties': {
337                 'order': [
338                     'job_number',
339                     'name',
340                     'description',
341                     'affiliation',
342                     'location',
343                     'operator',
344                     'room',
345                     'id_item_processed',
346                     'starting_date',
347                     'ending_date',
348                     'step_type',

```

```

349         'definition_of_process_step',
350         'recipe_name',
351         'recipe_file',
352         'developing_solution',
353         'developing_solution_proportions',
354         'developing_duration',
355         'developing_temperature',
356         'cleaning_solution',
357         'cleaning_solution_proportions',
358         'cleaning_duration',
359         'notes',
360     ]
361 },
362 },
363 )
364 developing_solution = Quantity(
365     type=str,
366     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
367 )
368 developing_solution_proportions = Quantity(
369     type=str,
370     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
371 )
372 developing_duration = Quantity(
373     type=np.float64,
374     a_eIn={
375         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
376         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'minute',
377     },
378     unit='minute',
379 )
380 developing_temperature = Quantity(
381     type=np.float64,
382     a_eIn={
383         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
384         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'celsius',
385     },
386     unit='celsius',
387 )
388 cleaning_solution = Quantity(
389     type=str,
390     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
391 )
392 cleaning_solution_proportions = Quantity(
393     type=str,
394     a_eIn={'component': 'StringEditQuantity'},
395 )
396 cleaning_duration = Quantity(
397     type=np.float64,
398     a_eIn={
399         'component': 'NumberEditQuantity',
400         'defaultDisplayUnit': 'sec',
401     },
402     unit='sec',
403 )

```

This class is similar to the wet cleaning class. The principle is to modify a material (in the case of wet cleaning remove) and then a cleaning step. With "developing" we labelled parameters useful in the actual developing step while with "cleaning" we described the parameters for the final cleaning.

Appendix B

Structure of the Json files

In the following are reported the JSONS files used to describe the ideal process

```
{
  "data": {
    "m_def": "fabrication_facilities.schema_packages.add.Spin_Coating",
    "name": "Coater Developer SVG8600 CRD base activity",
    "datetime": "2025-04-27T17:00:47.718706+00:00",
    "affiliation": "NFFA-DI",
    "step_type": "Coating",
    "id_item_processed": "W1",
    "short_name": "AR-P 6200.09",
    "spin_frequency": 4000,
    "instruments": [
      {
        "name": "Coater Developer SVG8600 - CRD Litho",
        "section":
          ↪ "../uploads/NAIwcr19QWCh3njQxvtloA/archive/fYN5rX4HI1hwLU-My7ecJs69LwWb#data"
      }
    ]
  }
}

{
  "data": {
    "m_def": "fabrication_facilities.schema_packages.transform.EBL",
    "name": "NanoLitho-EBL",
    "affiliation": "NFFA-DI",
    "location": "CNR-IFN@TN",
    "step_type": "Lithography",
    "id_item_processed": "W1",
    "dose": 100,
    "writing_field_dimension": 100,
    "address_size": 7,
    "current": 70,
    "tension": 30000,
    "alignment_required": true,
    "instruments": [
      {
        "name": "EBL Tescan NISABA-CRD NanoLitho",
        "section":
          ↪ "../uploads/NAIwcr19QWCh3njQxvtloA/archive/X0kUDyLN9ZmbKb5H92WW9eUBCRM#data"
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

```

    }
  ]
}

{
  "data": {
    "m_def": "fabrication_facilities.schema_packages.transform.ResistDevelopment",
    "developing_solution": "AR 600-546(CSAR 62dev)",
    "developing_duration": 1,
    "developing_temperature": 20,
    "stopping_solution": "IPA",
    "stopping_duration": 30,
    "instruments": [
      {
        "name": "Wet Bench SPM Wet Single Tank - CRD NanoLitho",
        "section":
          ↪ "../uploads/NAIwcr19QWCh3njQxvtloA/archive/mqpSNj4UKSLI0mqtI6Qp0y0-Wwbx#/data"
      }
    ],
    "cleaning_solution": "DIH20",
    "cleaning_duration": 30,
    "name": "CSAR 62 standard develop",
    "affiliation": "NFFA-DI",
    "location": "CNR-IFN@TN",
    "id_item_processed": "W1",
    "step_type": "Developing step"
  }
}

{
  "data": {
    "m_def": "fabrication_facilities.schema_packages.remove.DRIE",
    "name": "Poly-Si CH3-SF6 final part etch",
    "datetime": "2025-04-28T11:01:42.295248+00:00",
    "chemical_formula": "Si",
    "affiliation": "NFFA-DI",
    "location": "CNR-IFN@TN",
    "id_item_processed": "W1",
    "notes": "
    ↪ <p>Timed interleave cleaning is ok for this process</p>\n<p>Use polySi
    ↪ interleave recipe</p>\n<p>&nbsp;</p>\n<p>If a highly polymerizing has been
    ↪ performed beforehand, please ensure that a detailed O2 plasma cleaning (20-30 min
    ↪ with wafer on the chuck) has been performed before initiating this process,
    ↪ especially if the highly polymerizing process was longer than 30 min.</p>\n<p>Some
    ↪ examples of highly polymerizing processes include the following recipes saved in
    ↪ the etcher PC:</p>\n<p>&nbsp;</p>\n<ol>\n<li>SiO2 final full etch EP
    ↪ VERT</li>\n<li>SiO2 final full etch TIMED TEO</li>\n<li>SiO2 LP final full etch
    ↪ EP</li>\n<li>SiO2 LP final full etch TIMED</li>\n</ol>",
    "etching_rate_target": 260,
    "duration_target": 1,
    "short_name": "Poly-Si",
    "depth_target": 200,
    "fluximeters": [
      {
        "name": "SF6_flow",
        "datetime": "2025-04-28T11:05:41.949414+00:00",
        "chemical_formula": "SF6",
        "description": "
        ↪ <p>Unit in sccm</p>",
        "massflow": 16
      },
      {
        "name": "CH3F_flow",
        "datetime": "2025-04-28T11:05:41.955454+00:00",

```

```

    "chemical_formula": "CH3F",
    "description": "<p>Units in sccm</p>",
    "massflow":73
  }
],
}
}

```

All these steps are linked in the global process thanks to the following file:

```

{
  "data": {
    "m_def":
      ↪ "fabrication_facilities.schema_packages.fabrication_utilities.FabricationProcess",
    "id_proposal": "3855",
    "project": "EXT - MNF Collaborative Research_SD-MNF",
    "id_item_processed": "W1",
    "affiliation": "NFFA-DI",
    "locations": [
      "CNR-IFN@TN"
    ],
    "name": "EBL and RIE test",
    "author": "Damiano Giubertoni",
    "cost_model": "Moves Calculator",
    "steps": [
      "../uploads/NAIwcr19QWCh3njQxvtloA/archive/BtFKQE8io_ja2Y09tYhjNFsYMKE-#/data",
      "../uploads/NAIwcr19QWCh3njQxvtloA/archive/wJ5WOH-eIXpXML0Ums13JnOC4Bk8#/data",
      "../uploads/NAIwcr19QWCh3njQxvtloA/archive/G-vb2pWf9v19UParTnQRmxmvePN8#data",
      "../uploads/NAIwcr19QWCh3njQxvtloA/archive/GUi_SOMIfgQH_aTyu0wGQny3rRiv#data",
      "../uploads/NAIwcr19QWCh3njQxvtloA/archive/Y4DqCDTv3pcpeV25e3otEfVn8D0a#data"
    ]
  }
}

```

Navigating in the link [NOMAD Trento](#) is it possible to find more datasets, also of Equipment type and a try of sample parenting.

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